

TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY IN ZVOLEN

FACULTY OF FORESTRY

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**The Benefits of Forest Visits for the Health of Older Adults
during the COVID-19 Pandemic**

Dissertation thesis

**Kiki Ekiawan Lamatunga, MSc.
2023**

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**The Benefits of Forest Visits for the Health of Older Adults during
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Metodické pokyny na vypracovanie dizertačnej práce:

1. Štúdium literatúry týkajúce sa subjektívneho blahobytu a duševného zdravia starších dospelých. Príprava súčasného stavu v oblasti. Identifikácia ďalších medzier v existujúcich poznatkoch.
2. Príprava návrhu randomizovanej paralelnej štúdie s cieľom stanoviť účinok prechádzok v lesnom prostredí ako intervencie zameranej na kognitívne funkcie, znižovanie stresu a kvalitu života mestskom prostredí, s využitím prechádzok v urbánnom prostredí ako aktívnej kontroly.
3. Realizácia experimentu v trvaní 1 mesiaca, zahŕňajúca meranie variability srdcovej frekvencie, zber a analýzu vybraných biomarkérov a vykonávanie vybraných testov a prieskumov, ako test cesty a dotazník kvality života.
4. Zostavenie a vyhodnotenie výsledkov s použitím vhodných štatistických metód.
5. Interpretácia a diskusia výsledkov. Zhrnutie zistení a ich implikácií vo forme Záverov.

Dissertation thesis directives:

1. Study of literature regarding the subjective well-being and mental health of older adults. Preparation of the state-of-the-art in the field. Identification of knowledge gaps in addition to the established ones.
2. Preparation of the design for a randomized parallel study aimed to establish the effects of forest walking as an intervention focused on cognitive function, stress reduction, and the quality of life, while using urban walking as active control.
3. Implementation of a one-month experiment, involving the measurement of heart rate variability, collection and analyses of selected biomarkers, and the administration of selected tests and surveys, such as the trail-making test and quality of life questionnaire.
4. Compilation and evaluation of the results using appropriate statistical methods.
5. Interpretation and discussion of the results. Summarizing the results and their implications
Conclusions.

Zoznam odbornej literatúry:

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“Remembering the tumultuous storm that battered this journey, perhaps the collective initial expectations weren't fully met, yet from the scattered rubbles, a unique and novel unity is forged. Following the shadows through the night, a dawn of enlightenment arises, illuminating what was once concealed in profound darkness”

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Abstract

Examining the impact of the environment on the mental health of older adults is crucial in our aging society. Existing research on the restorative benefits of forests has largely overlooked older adults and, in most cases, focused only on group forest visits, which were restricted during the COVID-19 pandemic. This study explores the effects of individual walks on the mental health of adults aged 60 years or older in Slovakia. Through a randomized intervention study, participants were divided into groups walking in either forests or urban areas for 40 minutes over a month. The forest walking group exhibited significant improvements in cognitive flexibility, heart rate variability, and reduced acute and relative chronic stress levels, documented by Trail Making Test, photoplethysmography, and both salivary and hair cortisol measurements, respectively. The results were associated with forests featuring high species diversity and complex forest structures, typical in mixed forests with old trees. The respective patterns originated from natural processes or were achieved by more and less intense management for recreational purposes, illustrating manifold ways to ensure the desired, health- and subjective well-being-centered cultural ecosystem services of forests, specifically reflecting specific needs of older adults in the cognitive health domain.

While urban walking also benefits various quality-of-life aspects, forest walking is particularly notable for cognitive function enhancement. However, urban walking may be more suitable, convenient, or safer for frail older individuals, considering their sensitivity to factors impacting physical health. Specifically, walking in urban areas may be similarly beneficial as forest walking with regard to most of the quality-of-life components. However, when choosing between options available for walking in both forest and urban settings, the study findings strongly favor the former. The results underscore health- and subjective well-being-centered cultural ecosystem services of forests as crucial mental health support, including during crises for vulnerable groups like older adults. Integrating nature-based activities into mental health plans, specifically for these groups, is recommended. Collaboration between public health and forest management experts is vital to develop scalable frameworks focused on safe and accessible forest areas for older adults. Nature-based therapy enhances vitality and productivity in an extended retirement age context while ensuring green spaces benefit both individual and planetary well-being.

Keywords: forest and urban walking, older adults, cognitive flexibility, stress.

Abstrakt

Vzhľadom na demografický vývoj má výskum vplyvu prírodného prostredia na subjektívnu pohodu, kvalitu života a duševné zdravie v staršej populácii kľúčový význam. Doterajšie štúdie sa vo veľkej väčšine nezameriavali na starších ľudí a individuálne, ale takmer výlučne na skupinové návštevy lesov, ktoré však boli počas pandémie COVID-19 zakázané alebo obmedzené na minimum. Z týchto dôvodov naša štúdia skúma účinky individuálnych prechádzok v lesnom prostredí na duševné zdravie ľudí vo veku 60 rokov a starších. Účastníci randomizovanej intervenčnej štúdie boli alokovaní do dvoch skupín, v rámci ktorých absolvovali počas jedného mesiaca osem individuálnych 40-minútových prechádzok, buď v lesnom alebo urbánnom prostredí. Skupina jednotlivcov, ktorí absolvovali prechádzky v lese, vykázala významné zlepšenia v ukazovateľoch kognitívnej flexibility, variability srdcovej frekvencie, a zníženia akútneho a relatívneho chronického stresu, dokumentované testom cesty, fotopletysmografiou, a analýzou hladinou kortizolu v slinách a vo vlasoch. Pozitívne výsledky intervencie boli pozorované v lesnom prostredí, charakterizovanom pestrým drevinovým zložením, komplexnou porastovou štruktúrou a prítomnosťou starých stromov. Tieto vlastnosti rezultovali z prírodných procesov, resp. manažmentu prihliadajúceho na podporu rekreačného a zdravotného aspektu kultúrnych ekosystémových služieb lesov. Komplexné štruktúry prítomné v takýchto lesoch zodpovedajú špecifickým potrebám starších dospelých v oblasti kognitívneho zdravia.

Prechádzky v mestskom prostredí môžu byť podobne prospešné v ukazovateľoch väčšiny komponentov kvality života. Pre zraniteľných starších jedincov môžu byť vhodnejšou alternatívou, zohľadňujúcou citlivosť na faktory ovplyvňujúce fyzické zdravie. Pri možnosti výberu medzi oboma alternatívami za rovnakých podmienok však získané výsledky podporujú výber prechádzok alebo intervencie v lesnom prostredí. Kultúrne ekosystémové služby lesov preto zohrávajú kľúčovú úlohu v podpore duševného zdravia staršej populácie, vrátane krízových situácií, akou bola pandémia COVID-19. Preto je potrebná ich integrácia do plánov duševného zdravia s dôrazom na potreby staršej populácie, najmä prístupnosť a bezpečnosť. Na to je nevyhnutná spolupráca odborníkov z oblastí verejného zdravia a lesníctva. Rekreačia v lesnom prostredí zároveň podporuje aj vitalitu a produktivitu v kontexte rastúceho veku odchodu do dôchodku, pričom lesy vhodné na rekreáciu prispievajú nielen k individuálnemu, ale aj k planétarnemu blahobytu.

Kľúčové slová: prechádzky v lesnom a mestskom prostredí, staršia populácia, kognitívna flexibilita, stress.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATION

APA	American Psychological Association
ART	Attention Restoration Theory
BMD	Bone mineral density
BMI	Body mass index
CDC	Centres for Disease Control and Prevention
CES	Cultural ecosystem services
CgA	Chromogranin A
DASS-21	Depression anxiety stress scales
DBP	Diastolic blood pressure
DM	Diabetes mellitus
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
DSM-5	Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders-5 th edition
ECT	Electroconvulsive therapy
EHRV	Elite heart rate variability
ELISA	Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay
ES	Ecosystem services
ESC	European Society of Cardiology
FES	Forest ecosystem services
fMRI	functional magnetic resonance imaging
GDP	Gross domestic product
GDPR	General data protection regulation
GPS	Global positioning system
HCC	Hair cortisol concentration
HDL	High density lipoprotein
HR	Heart rate
HRV	Heart rate variability
ISOQOL	International Society for Quality of Life Research
MBSR	Mindfulness based stress reduction
MCI	Mild cognitive impairment
MEA	Millennium ecosystem assessment
NASPE	National Association for Support and Physical Education
NDVI	Normalized difference vegetation index
NFC	Near field communication
NIEHS	National Institute of Environmental Health Science
NIH	National Institutes of Health
NIR	Near infrared
PIR-R/+R	Passive infrared (red)
PPG	Photoplethysmography
RCT	Randomized controlled trial
RMSSD	Root mean square of successive differences
ROS	Reactive oxygen species
RRT	Relational restoration theory
SAA	Salivary alpha-amylase
SCC	Salivary cortisol concentration
SPB	Systolic blood pressure
SWB	Subjective well-being

TEEB	The economics of ecosystem and biodiversity
TMS	Transcranial magnetic stimulation
UN	United Nation
UNDESA	United Nation Department of Economic and Social Affairs
USGS	United States Geological Survey
WHO	World Health Organization

1. INTRODUCTION

The demand for nature and forests as recreational and restorative environments has increasingly shaped forestry and interdisciplinary research since several decades. More than 40 years ago, Papánek (1978), in his seminal work “Theory and Practice of Functionally Integrated Forest Management”, recognized the growing importance of forest recreation and the human health benefits derived from time spent in forests, as well as the “explosive character” of forest recreation, both in terms of the number of forest visitors and its impact on forest ecosystems. At the same time, he proposed methods for the integration of forest recreation and health-related functions in forestry planning and management. In the following decades, health-related and other forest functions have been progressively recast into the ecosystem services framework, in which functions providing benefits to concrete populations and populations segments are considered ecosystem services. In other words, while the ecosystem functions include the physicochemical and biological processes that occur within the ecosystems and support terrestrial life, ecosystem services are the set of ecosystem functions that are directly linked to benefit human well-being (Kremen, 2005). Forest biomes provide a great share of ecosystem services at the global scale and acknowledging the value of forest ecosystem services (FES) is critically important towards sustainable decision making (Grammatikopoulou & Vačkárová, 2021).

While forests as restorative environments and health-related FES are essential for the well-being of the global population (Jenkins & Schaap, 2018), they are of vital importance for vulnerable groups such as older adults (Konijnendijk et al., 2023). This is because one of the recent global population trends is the rise of the aging population. In total, the world's aging population accounts for 9.7% and is projected to grow by 16.4% in the following three decades. There are multiple reasons, but economic factors play a major role in driving this trend. Data from the United Nations (2022) revealed that Europe and North America currently lead with 18.7% of the population aged 65 year and older. Economic prosperity reflected by the higher values of GDP per capita is identified as a key factor contributing positively to the growth of this population (Miladinov, 2020). Over the years, economic growth, especially in developed nations, has coincided with increased educational opportunities (Lazerson, 1998), advancements in healthcare and pharmaceuticals (Zarros & Tansey, 2019), and improved living conditions (Matsubara, 1969). Collectively, these factors contribute to a decline in morbidity and mortality rates. Moreover, governmental

policies and societal security systems have adapted to these evolving trends, ensuring an enhanced quality of life for this aging population (Aranco et al., 2022). However, the demographic shift towards an aging population is not without hurdles and governments are under pressure to strategically address the increasing health and retirement needs of the elderly by implementing policies that ensure their well-being but keep the economy growing (Lee & Mason, 2017).

One of the key issues facing the elderly in the present time is mental health-related illnesses, e.g., depression, anxiety, and cognitive decline, along with multimorbidity (Ma, 2020; Zhou et al., 2023). Various factors cause mental disorders in older adults, which ranges from individual drivers (e.g., biological changes, chronic health condition, polypharmacy, trauma and PTSD, or adverse childhood experience, etc.) to psychosocial and environmental drivers (e.g. social isolation, loss and grief, financial stress during post-retirement, lack of access to mental health care, as well as the onset of pandemic such as COVID-19) (Gao et al., 2023; Lin et al., 2011; Assary & Bazargan, 2019; Glaesmer et al., 2011; Pietrzak et al 2012; Li et al., 2023; NASEM, 2020; Schladitz et al., 2021; Marshall et al., 2020; PAN, 2021; Xu et al., 2023; Baranyi et al., 2021; Bafail, 2022).

In response to that, exposure to nature and forests through nature-based therapy offers manifold restorative benefits for human health and well-being. Numerous studies have investigated the influence of nature-based therapy on various physiological markers, revealing compelling outcomes. For instance, exposure to natural settings during therapy sessions has been associated with a decrease in salivary cortisol levels, indicating a potential reduction in stress (Kaimal et al., 2016). The impact on heart rate variability (HRV) has also been examined, showing patterns consistent with a more relaxed physiological state, suggesting a positive influence on the autonomic nervous system (Heiss et al., 2021). Moreover, nature-based therapy has been linked to favorable changes in blood pressure, contributing to the stabilization of cardiovascular responses (Qiu et al., 2023). The inherent calming and restorative qualities of nature, integral to nature-based therapy, play a crucial role in fostering positive shifts in individuals' physiological states (Hansen et al., 2017).

On psychological responses, nature-based intervention is associated with positive changes in mood, reduced levels of anxiety and depression, and an overall enhancement in mental well-being (Hartig et al., 1996; Karjalainen et al., 2010; Jarosz, 2022; Pichlerová et al., 2023). Exposure to natural settings has been linked to improved attention, concentration, and cognitive performance (Schertz et al., 2019). Additionally, nature-based therapy has been shown to foster a sense of connection to the environment (Mayer & Frantz, 2004) and

a heightened appreciation for the beauty of nature (Diessner & Steiner, 2017), contributing to emotional well-being (Richardson et al., 2019; Zelensky et al., 2014). The restorative qualities of nature, including its ability to provide a sense of calm and tranquility, play a pivotal role in promoting positive psychological responses (Kaplan, 1995). In essence, nature-based therapy emerges as a promising avenue for enhancing mental health by positively influencing various psychological aspects, ultimately contributing to a holistic sense of well-being.

Nature exposure also induces a change in attitudes towards physical activity and behavioral control as an effect of the aforementioned benefits. Calogiuri & Chroni (2014) systematically reviewed 99 studies investigating the relationship between natural environment and physical activity and found 22 studies reported engaging with natural environment encouraged people to be physically active. In the realm of physical activity, it predicts walking when a natural environment is available (Rhodes et al., 2006) and influences outdoor recreation participation (Kouthouris & Spontis, 2005). Experimental studies demonstrate that positive experiences in physical activity enhance attitudes, perceived behavioral control, and intentions for future physical activity engagement. The environment, particularly whether physical activity occurs indoors or outdoors, significantly influences emotional responses. Research indicates that walking outdoors, compared to indoor treadmill walking, is associated with increased enjoyment, positive emotions, and a higher intention to participate in future physical activity (Dasilva et al., 2011; Whittemore et al., 2005). Enhanced attitudes and perceived behavioral control are therefore fostered by positive experiences in nature, consequently promoting engagement in physical activity (Calogiuri & Chroni, 2014). Other benefits on cognitive, social, psychological responses, etc., acquired when engaging with natural-based activities collectively contribute to a healthier, more active lifestyle, potentially reducing the prevalence of obesity and promoting optimal BMI (Ellaway et al., 2005), better sleep quality (Shin et al., 2020), and improved social connectivity (Jennings & Bamkole, 2019).

Expanding understanding of the health advantages linked to forests underscores the necessity for integrating this awareness into health policy creation and forest management planning. Recognizing forests' pivotal role as providers of vital ecosystem services is crucial (Vining & Tyler, 1999; Levy et al., 2012). To optimize the benefits from forest exposure and customize forest management to meet specific human requirements, a more profound comprehension of woodland experiences—comprising exposure frequency and duration—is imperative (Milcu et al., 2013; Doimo et al., 2020). This knowledge is especially valuable

in addressing the escalating demand for alternative health interventions like nature-based therapy. This demand is driven by challenges related to healthcare accessibility, rising medical treatment costs, and mental healthcare needs (de Beurs et al., 1999; Rowan et al., 2013) and other associated factors.

Inspection of the available literature reveals that there is a scarcity of research addressing vulnerable populations, particularly older adults. In addition, most of the intervention studies were conducted in group settings, with a main focus on short-term intervention, particularly for biomarker outcomes. Also, a great majority of interventions took place in parks, semi-urban, and urban forests, in which the subjects did not experience the whole range of factors typical of ordinary, managed, semi-natural or natural forests, such as remoteness from populated areas, common wildlife or environments unadjusted for primary recreational purposes. Therefore, our research aimed to address these and other gaps identified in the research of the cultural FES related to health benefits offered by forests to older adults. Relatedly, it was anticipated that the results would also inform the management of forests intended as restorative environments, including for older adults.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The section provides a concise presentation of the current key theories, concepts, and findings elucidating why and how time spent in forests may benefit the health of elderly adults. The section looks at this important topic from an interdisciplinary perspective, since forest benefits to human health—and the health of elderly adults in particular—lay at the intersection of the physical and mental health, as well as the physicochemical and biological basis of forest ecosystems patterns and processes. These properties sustain health benefits of forests as a fundamental component of the cultural FES. It is therefore crucial to understand which pathways between exposure to forest environment and the subjective well-being and mental health of older adults could be used and targeted by forest interventions. This section also points out several gaps in the existing body of knowledge, which our research intended to address.

2.1 Theory of aging

Aging, or senescence, is an inherent and gradual process experienced by humans throughout their lifespan, marked by an accumulation of progressive bodily changes that contribute to disease progression, disability, and ultimately death (Harman, 1981). This natural phenomenon involves dynamic alterations in biological, physiological, psychological, environmental, and social processes (NIH, 2020). Strehler (1977) conceptualized aging as universal (occurring in varying degrees in all living beings), intrinsic (not dependent on external causes), progressive (continuously changing throughout life), and deleterious (resulting in the degradation of various body systems).

Biological and physiological changes associated with aging often manifest as a decline in the physical functioning of specific organs. Muscle mass may decrease by 1–2% annually after age 50 and continues to diminish with advancing age (Chodzko-Zajko et al., 2009). Bone mineral density (BMD) tends to decline by about 0.5% per year during middle age for both sexes. The active range of motion in joints may decrease by approximately 20–30% after the age of 70 years (Chodzko-Zajko et al., 2009; Gregson, 2017). While certain aspects of the nervous system, such as the speed of cognitive processing and movement, might decrease, problem-solving skills and the capacity for new learning typically remain intact. Sleep duration tends to shorten, potentially leading to cognitive impairment (Galvin, 2017). In the cardiovascular system, arterial walls thicken due to fibrosis and increased collagen

cross-linking, contributing to a decline in endothelial function and an increase in systolic blood pressure (Chodzko-Zajko et al., 2009; Howlett, 2017). In myocytes and pacemaker cells, oxygen consumption decreases. The lung's forced expiration volumes at the alveolar surface may decrease (Davies & Bolton, 2017). Hormone levels, including growth hormone, thyroid hormones, estrogen, and testosterone, often decrease by around 1% per year after the age of 30 (Morley & McKee, 2017). The immune system weakens as the thymus gland shrinks, resulting in decreased production of T cell and B cell lymphocytes in the bone marrow (Tummala et al., 2017). The genitourinary system experiences decreased glomerular filtration, nephron number, and size, while bladder fibrosis may lead to reduced bladder capacity and increased voiding frequency (Smith, 2017). Vision may be impaired as lens accommodation for near vision diminishes (Whiteside et al., 2006), and hearing might decline due to the loss of hair cells in the cochlea, with age-related hearing loss independently associated with dementia (Chern & Golub, 2019). The integument undergoes changes, including the loss of hair pigment, wrinkling, a decrease in sweat gland activity, and reduced productivity of sebaceous glands (Tobin et al., 2017).

Age-associated psychological changes are marked profoundly in cognitive and mental health. Short-term memory shows significant changes with age, but long-term memory deteriorates less with age. Besides, slower reactions and reduced problem-solving are inevitably experienced as people age (APA, 2021). Viña et al. (2007) compiled theories of aging in three main aspects: genetic mutation, cellular waste accumulation, and wear and tear theory. Each of them has sub-theories that intersect each other, which are depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Classification of theories of aging. Adapted from Viña et al. (2007).

The theory of antagonistic pleiotropy posits that aging is a byproduct of genes selected for their contributions to fertility and other essential aspects of individual fitness (Mitteldorf, 2019). For instance, higher testosterone levels in younger males may enhance fitness, but these levels decrease in later life due to their association with prostate cancer risk. The accumulative waste theory suggests that molecules damaged by oxidation and their byproducts, such as aged collagen and damaged enzymes, accumulate in nondividing cells, leading to dysfunction, toxicity, aging, and cell death (Diggs, 2007). The free radical theory contends that aging results from the accumulation of damage inflicted by reactive oxygen species (ROS) within cells, causing harm to DNA and other cellular structures (Gladyshev, 2014). The insulin resistance theory links aging to reduced glucose effectiveness, increased hepatic insulin extraction, and decreased glucose sensitivity in the second stage of insulin secretion (Refaie et al., 2006). According to the advanced glycation theory, glycation or glucose binding to molecules such as lipids and proteins has significant effects (e.g., diabetes, atherosclerosis, neurodegeneration, kidney diseases) later in life (Chen et al., 2022). Telomeres and the Hayflick theory highlight bits of DNA at the ends of chromosomes that protect them from sticking or tangling, with telomeres shortening as cells replicate, correlating with cellular aging or senescence (Barlett, 2015). The error catastrophe theory posits that senescence results from the accumulation of errors in cellular molecules crucial for function and reproduction, leading to a catastrophic event incompatible with cellular survival. The autoimmunity theory suggests that aging induces the loss of immune system efficiency and widespread dysfunction, demonstrated by autoimmunity (Diggs, 2007). The circadian regulation theory proposes that the circadian system significantly influences aging and longevity (Hood & Amir, 2017). Finally, the evolutionary theory is a classic explanation for the rise in fatality with age. As aging progresses, there is a decline in lifetime fertility, and continued survival has diminishing effects on reproductive fitness. Successful reproduction often involves intergenerational transfers in addition to fertility (Guillot et al., 2022).

2.2 Mental health in the aging population

Mental health, according to WHO, is “the state of mental well-being that enables people to cope with the stresses of life, realize their abilities, learn well and work well, and contribute to their community.” Meanwhile, mental illness encompasses a group of identifiable mental disorders characterized by notable alterations in cognition, emotions, and/or behavior, causing distress and/or impairments in social or familial functioning

(Njoku, 2022). Someone with mental illness is diagnosed after a thorough clinical assessment or other reliable and validated tools and then categorized based on Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5) by mental health professionals (APA, 2022).

Mental health-related issues are projected to become the leading cause of worldwide global burden by overtaking cardiovascular disease in 2030. Depression, stress, anxiety, and dementia are the most common mental illnesses in seniors, leading to other health issues, disability, comorbidities, and lowered cognitive function and quality of life (WHO, 2023). Several recent causes of this phenomenon, particularly for older adults are due to chronic pain (Lin et al., 2011), physical disability (Cree et al., 2020), traumatic events (Glaesmer et al., 2011), financial issues (Marshall et al., 2020), global communicable diseases such as COVID-19 (Bafail, 2022), and, last but not least, the environmental influence (Helbich, 2018), which involves both the direct and indirect impact on human life.

Through the available remedies that experts have developed, including the most common treatment such as psychotherapy, cognitive behavioral therapy, medication, hospitalization, and rehabilitation, to the more advanced methods, including ECT (Electroconvulsive Therapy), TMS (Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation), and other brain stimulation therapies, will reduce a person's annual physical health care costs by 20 percent, and if mental distress such as depression, anxiety, and other types are tackled effectively, this will boost GDP by 4% (Layard, 2016). While not everyone can access a mental health therapist due to socioeconomic disparities, the profound capacity of nature and forests to restore physical and mental well-being is considerable. Consequently, this aspect has been the subject of intense research.

2.3 Forest ecosystem services and human health

Forests are integral components of ecosystems, providing a diverse range of services crucial for environmental stability, biodiversity preservation, and human well-being (Brockhoff et al., 2017). Ecosystem services (ES) denote the advantages derived by individuals from natural elements, inherent processes, or the operational functions of ecosystems. The ES delivery is contingent upon societal values, objectives, aspirations, and gains, as highlighted by the findings of Bishop et al. (2010) and Kelble et al. (2013). These services encompass three key categories: provisioning services, regulating services, and cultural services, extending beyond the fundamental ecosystem functions. The ability of forest ecosystems to furnish ecosystem services depends upon their condition, assessed

through diverse indicators as indicated by Sing et al. (2015). Provisioning services involve tangible resources such as timber and non-timber forest products, encompassing fruits, nuts, mushrooms, and medicinal plants, contributing to livelihoods, traditional practices, and global trade. Regulating ecosystem services, particularly those from forests and trees, play vital roles in climate regulation, carbon sequestration, and climate change mitigation (van den Bosch & Bird, 2018). Forests significantly impact climate conditions, water cycles, soil erosion prevention, air purification, and the maintenance of clean air and water resources. Additionally, these forested areas act as crucial barriers against natural disasters like floods and landslides. Forests hold immense cultural and recreational significance and thus provide important cultural ecosystem services. Integral to cultural practices, folklore, and spiritual beliefs, forests offer spaces for recreation, ecotourism, and aesthetic appreciation, contributing to mental and emotional well-being. The cultural services provided by forests strengthen the connection between communities and the natural world. Nevertheless, external pressures leading to ecosystem degradation can compromise both the quantity and quality of these anticipated services (Fleischer et al., 2017).

From a human health perspective, the cultural ecosystem services derived from forests, trees, and green spaces make substantial contributions to well-being, transcending their aesthetic allure (Konijnendijk et al., 2023). These natural settings afford opportunities for recreational activities, exerting positive impacts on both mental and physical well-being, thereby cultivating healthier residential and occupational environments. The multifaceted services rendered by forest ecosystems not only augment the overall quality of life but also exhibit the potential to alleviate cognitive decline and dementia, addressing pertinent risk factors such as physical inactivity, loneliness, and air pollution (Livingston et al., 2020).

Especially for the elderly, green spaces, including forests and trees, act as protective factors for mental health, exhibiting promising associations with reduced depression risks (Brown et al., 2018; Zhou et al., 2022). Interventions like forest therapy and increased exposure to nature have demonstrated significant improvements in quality-of-life measures among older adults (Oh et al., 2017). Although existing studies indicate positive correlations, further in-depth research is necessary to understand nuanced effects across diverse populations and geographical regions. The critical role of forest ecosystems in sustaining human health and well-being is underscored by the essential ecosystem services they provide.

2.3.1 Conceptual models of cultural ecosystem services and health

Cultural ecosystem services (CES) and health outcomes provide valuable frameworks for understanding the multifaceted connections between human well-being and cultural interactions with nature. According to Pröbstl-Haider (2015), various research domains contribute to the interdisciplinary exploration of CES, health, and well-being. Each domain is grounded in distinct hermeneutics and research traditions, frequently overlapping. Within these domains, CES research commonly encompasses (i) medical evidence focusing on indicators such as blood pressure, heart rate, or stress hormones, (ii) psychological concepts from environmental psychology or health psychology, (iii) observational evidence derived from exposure to nature, often through public surveys and medical databases, and (iv) economic concepts and methods, exemplified by the life satisfaction approach, e.g. Hirons et al. (2016). The models draw on diverse disciplines, including ecology, psychology, sociology, and public health, to unravel the complex pathways through which CES contributes to health effects. Several key conceptual models that explain how CES and health are connected are presented below:

Health Capability Model

The Health Capability Model, inspired by Amartya Sen's (1979, 1988) capabilities approach, emphasizes that health is not merely the absence of disease but the ability to lead a flourishing life. In the context of CES, this model asserts that cultural interactions with nature contribute to expanding individuals' health capabilities. CES promotes opportunities for individuals to access cultural amenities in nature, fostering a sense of autonomy, social connectedness, and overall well-being.

Biopsychosocial Model

The Biopsychosocial Model conceptualized by Engel (1977) integrates biological, psychological, and social dimensions to explain health outcomes. In relation to CES, this model recognizes that cultural engagements with nature influence physiological responses, psychological states, and social dynamics. Exposure to culturally significant landscapes, rituals, or practices in nature may lead to positive emotional experiences, reduced stress, and strengthened social bonds, all of which contribute to improved health.

Ecological Public Health Model

The Ecological Public Health model elaborated by Hancock (1993) extends the

traditional public health perspective by acknowledging the interconnectedness of ecological systems and human health. Within this model, CES is seen as a determinant of health, shaping lifestyle choices, social interactions, and community well-being. Cultural practices embedded in nature, such as ceremonies, celebrations, or artistic expressions, contribute to a supportive ecological context that fosters health-promoting behaviors.

Socio-Ecological Model

Bronfenbrenner's Socio-Ecological Model (1970s) posits that health outcomes are influenced by interactions between individuals and their social and environmental contexts. CES is positioned within this model as a key component of the environmental context, shaping individuals' perceptions, behaviors, and social relationships. Access to culturally significant natural spaces and practices influences health through pathways related to physical activity, stress reduction, and social engagement.

2.3.2 Dimensions of cultural ecosystem services and health well-being

Cultural ecosystem services have both spatial (place-based) and temporal dimensions (Flood et al., 2021; Csurgó & Smith, 2022). While the former coincides mainly with recreation, aesthetics, and tourism, the latter primarily focuses on heritage aspects but is equally concerned with aspects such as the duration and frequency of forest visits and related activities, pivotal for achieving desired restorative effects. For example, White et al. (2019) postulated that spending at least 120 minutes per week in contact with nature is associated with well-being and good health. However, this minimum time may reflect a broader definition of the natural environment, including city parks and farmland. A targeted forest-based intervention could lead to a reduction in the minimum required exposure duration. Moreover, spatial and temporal dimensions often touch upon each other and partly overlap.

2.3.2.1 Recreation, aesthetics, tourism, and human health

The relationship between recreation, aesthetics, and human health is a subject of growing interest, with research consistently demonstrating the positive impact of nature on physical activity and mental health, as well as the profound influence of aesthetic preferences on emotional well-being (Pasanen et al., 2014). This exploration delves into two key aspects, consisting in the effect of nature on physical activity and mental health, and the role of aesthetic preferences in forming emotional well-being. Nature has a compelling influence on physical activity, as natural environments often serve as attractive settings for recreational

pursuits. Studies consistently show that individuals engaging in physical activities in natural settings, such as hiking, jogging, or cycling experience enhanced well-being (Lawton et al., 2017). Also, being in nature acts as a motivating factor, leading individuals to engage in more prolonged and enjoyable physical activities compared to indoor settings (Sallis & Owen, 2002; Yang et al., 2021). Further, mental health frequently benefits from exposure to nature, which has a profound impact on mental well-being. The concept of nature therapy or ecotherapy emphasizes the therapeutic benefits of outdoor recreation. Natural environments are associated with reduced stress, anxiety, and depression (Thompson et al., 2012; Beyer et al., 2014). The tranquility and aesthetic beauty of nature contribute to improved mood, increased attention, and enhanced cognitive functions (Franco et al., 2017; Jimenez et al., 2021).

Consequently, nature is considered a restorative environment that allows individuals to recover from mental fatigue and stress. The Attention Restoration Theory (ART) posits that exposure to nature facilitates involuntary attention, providing relief from the demands of sustained focus, and promoting mental restoration (Kaplan & Kaplan, 1989). In addition to that, human aesthetic preferences, especially in the context of natural environments, play a pivotal role in shaping emotional well-being. Aesthetic experiences derived from nature contribute significantly to positive emotional states and overall life satisfaction (Fuller, 2012; Sæther, 2019). Further, individuals often express aesthetic preferences for certain natural landscapes, such as scenic vistas, water bodies, or lush greenery. Personal preferences influence the perceived beauty and appeal of environments, impacting the emotional response. And conversely, the perceptual properties of the natural environment experiences of its restorative potential, and one's actions in—and interactions with—the environment also shape the corresponding preferences (Beute & de Kort, 2018). Aesthetic experiences in nature evoke positive emotions, including awe, wonder, and serenity. Relatedly, exposure to aesthetically pleasing environments is associated with reduced stress levels and increased feelings of happiness. The aesthetic quality of the environment contributes to emotional restoration and psychological resilience (Løvoll et al., 2020; Ingulli & Lindbloom, 2013). Last but not least, the biophilia hypothesis suggests that humans have an innate affinity for nature, and exposure to natural aesthetics aligns with our evolutionary history, fostering positive emotional responses. Nature's aesthetic elements, such as fractals, patterns, and colors, contributes to emotional well-being (Wilson, 1984).

2.3.2.2 Spiritual and cultural heritage

Understanding the complex relationship between spiritual connection to nature, mental health, and cultural heritage preservation is essential for holistic well-being. This exploration delves into two vital aspects: the role of spiritual connection to nature in mental health and the significance of cultural heritage preservation for community well-being. Spiritual connection to nature refers to the deep, intrinsic bond individuals feel with the natural world, transcending the physical and engaging the spiritual dimension (Pirri, 2019). This connection has profound implications for mental health and well-being, as does transcendental experience. Individuals who experience a spiritual connection to nature often report a sense of transcendence, awe, and reverence (Bethelmy & Corraliza, 2019). These experiences have been linked to positive mental health outcomes, including reduced stress, anxiety, and depressive symptoms.

Furthermore, spiritual connection to nature provides individuals with a sense of meaning and purpose (Egri, 1997). The awe-inspiring elements of nature evoke feelings of interconnectedness, contributing to a sense of belonging and purpose in the larger tapestry of life. This sense of purpose is a protective factor against mental health challenges. Mindfulness and presence also play a role in the subjective well-being and nature often serves as a natural setting for mindfulness practices. Spiritual connection to nature fosters a state of presence and mindfulness, promoting mental clarity, emotional regulation, and overall psychological well-being. Nature becomes a sanctuary for reflection and introspection (Gordon et al., 2018) and plays a substantial role in sustaining identity a belonging (Häggström, 2019). Often, nature and forests constitute a part of nations' cultural heritage fostering positive self-esteem and mental well-being (Roberts & Burleson, 2013), enhancing community mental health (Makwana, 2019), and strengthening generational bonds positively impacting the mental health of both younger and older community members (Whear et al., 2023).

2.3.3 Knowledge gap in cultural ecosystem services and health outcomes:

The gap in understanding cultural ecosystem services (CES) and their impact on health outcomes primarily arises from insufficient exploration of cultural diversity and context sensitivity, such as variations across cultural contexts. Research has been limited regarding CES across specific focus groups, especially older adults, habitats, or ecosystems. Additionally, inadequate attention has been given to long-term health effects, longitudinal studies, and the cumulative impact on an individual's lifespan. Limited collaboration among

ecologists, cultural experts, and medical professionals contributes to this gap. Thus, there's a pressing need for multidisciplinary research involving experts across diverse fields to comprehensively address the intricate interactions between ecosystems, culture, and human health (Cabana et al., 2020; Satz et al., 2013; Slovák et al., 2023; Cheng, 2023; Pröbstl-Haider, 2015; Naumann et al., 2021; Hedin et al., 2022).

2.4 Mechanism of natural environment and mental health

The natural environment serves as the milieu from which all entities derived from the surrounding elements of nature emanate (Lauesen, 2013). Within the context of this dissertation, the term “natural environments” encompasses a spectrum of green spaces, comprising forests, parks, meadows, scrublands, grasslands, nature reserves, and others. Nevertheless, the primary nature-based intervention employed in this study predominantly revolves around forested environments.

Forest bathing, forest therapy, nature-based therapy, ecotherapy, or nature “pill” exposure are some of the terms that refer to the practice of involving oneself in forested or natural environments to gain resilient physical and mental health. It was introduced earlier in ancient Japanese culture, well-known as “Shinrin-Yoku” (Hansen et al., 2017). In the Western world, Ulrich (1983) postulated that the natural environment has a restorative effect that alleviates stress, also known as stress reduction theory (STR). Kaplan (1989) posited the power of nature can improve one's cognitive function, also widely known as attention restoration theory (ART). In modern science, forest therapy has been documented in many research settings. A meta-analysis from Coventry et al. (2021) collected 50 RCT studies on the mental and physical health of healthy adults and found that nature-based interventions were effective for improving depressive mood, reducing anxiety, improving positive effects, and reducing negative effects. The nature-based activities reported to effectively predict the outcomes were gardening, green exercise, and nature-based therapy. They also affected those with pre-existing mental health problems. Furthermore, Yao et al. (2021) specifically determined stress reduction that showed ramifications on various mental health responses such as salivary cortisol, state of anxiety, self-reported stress, blood pressure, heart rate variability, and restorative outcomes. Additionally, during crisis periods such as the COVID-19 plague, the forest restoration effect was tremendously helpful in tackling loneliness or boredom which was reflected by the increased number of forest visits (Pichlerová et al., 2021; Jarský et al., 2022).

Phytoncides, or the volatile essential oils emitted by plants, particularly trees, are one of the critical elements behind the power of nature on human health. Most of the trees that generate phytoncides are pine, fir, cedar, oak, or minute plants like garlic. These organic compounds have been proven to have antimicrobial properties and can contribute to immune systems. A randomized control trial by Li et al. (2009) assigned 55 gynecological cancer survivors to a space that was scented with phytoncide aromas vs a non-scented space. The intervention group had a lower stress level and had an increase in natural killer (NK) cells (effector lymphocytes of the innate immune system) in comparison to those who were allocated to the control group. Subsequently, in a more natural setting, a study that involved Japanese adults (both female and male) with a two-night trip to the forest area, was found that the mean values of natural killer cell activity, and the numbers of NK cell, granulysin, perforin, and granzymes A/B expressing cells on forest bathing days were profoundly higher than in a control group. On the other hand, the concentration of urinary adrenaline on forest bathing days was significantly higher in the control setting in both sexes (Li, 2010).

The experimental functional MRI study by Kim et al. (2010) revealed that rural scenery such as forests, gardens, and hills activated the anterior cingulate gyrus, globus pallidus, putamen, and head of the caudate nucleus, which is responsible for cognitive function, emotional expression, mood allocation, and depth of love. Whereas, urban scenery is associated with the hippocampus, parahippocampus, and amygdala, which are accountable for stress buffering or resilience-enhancing factors against depression and negative stressful events (Yamamoto et al., 2017). Studies have also revealed a greater advantage in improving quality of life by engaging with the natural environment. Dzhambov et al. (2018) found that the serial mediation model of greenspace to restorative quality, social cohesion, and physical activity indicated better mental health, which leads to a satisfied body and mind. A large amount of greenery is associated with less mental stress, and greater happiness (White et al., 2013), and greater neighborhood provision of public parks from childhood through to adulthood may help to slow down the rate of cognitive decline in later life (Cherrie et al., 2018), a short recreation program might be effective to reduce negative stress symptoms (Bielinis et al., 2019), and thus, people are more satisfied and happier with communities with more greenspace.

Many pathways have been explored to establish plausible links between nature and health in many different settings and focus by, e.g., Hartig et al. (2014) and Kuo (2015). Since they are pioneers in the comprehensive research of the health benefits of nature for people, we synthesized the pathways between nature and human well-being proposed by

them in Figure 2. The plausible mechanisms had to meet the following criteria: to be measured objectively; had been theorized to show causality ties; nature, and mechanism association have been demonstrated with controlling socioeconomic characteristics; mechanism and health outcomes were independent with nature. Essentially, the 21 suggested pathways include environmental factors, physiological and psychological states, and behavior conditions. Subsequently, they were compartmentalized into layered clusters. The first layer comprises biological drivers, physical environmental drivers, and biophilic elements. The second layer consists of physiological states, psychological and emotional restoration, and behavioral states, as they contribute to human health and well-being outcomes.

Overall, when individuals interface with the natural environment, they undergo exposure to environmental elements or agent ingredients that directly impact both their physiological and psychological states, thereby exerting an indirect influence on their holistic health and well-being. Behaviors and conditions emerge as ubiquitous determinants that empirically shape health and well-being, elucidating their mediating role in the complex interplay between nature exposure and health outcomes. As research in this field is growing fast, the most recent approach addressing the Psycho-Neuro-Endocrine-Immunology (P.N.E.I) network as a new concept of forest medicine has just been published by Li (2023).

Figure 2. Pathways between nature and human well-being. Adapted from Hartig et al. (2014) and Kuo (2015).

2.5 Healthy aging measures

The World Health Organization (2020) defined healthy aging as the “process of developing and maintaining the functional ability that enables well-being in older age”. A recent study from Behr et al. (2023) synthesized 74 studies on healthy aging and found that there were three main tools for identifying aspects of healthy aging: bio and performance markers (e.g., physiological function, cognitive function, immune function, and endocrine function), questionnaires (e.g., physical functioning, psychological well-being, emotional factors, social participation, and context factors), and scores (e.g., combined multiple aspects and non-binary scores). The presented dissertation focused on four functions, which are elucidated below.

2.5.1 Physiological function (heart rate variability)

While heart rate denotes the count of heartbeats per minute, heart rate variability (HRV) is the fluctuation or variation in time intervals between adjacent heartbeats (McCraty & Shaffer, 2015). It is one of the proxies for determining psychological reactions such as stress, anxiety, depression, and many other health-related problems. HRV serves as an index reflecting neurocardiac function, shaped by heart-brain interactions and the autonomic nervous system (ANS) (Shaffer & Ginsberg, 2017). The ANS, governing heart rate, blood pressure, respiration, digestion, vascular tone, and more, communicates with the hypothalamus, directing bodily functions to activate or relax (Lanki et al., 2017). Higher HRV values correlate with enhanced self-control, adeptness in handling negative emotions, and confidence in social interactions. Conversely, lower HRV is linked to psychological distress, though exceptions exist, especially in certain pathological episodes like cardiac conduction abnormalities, associated with increased HRV and heightened risk of elderly fatality (Shaffer & Ginsberg, 2017). HRV is assessed through various metrics: long-term HRV (24h), short-term (~5 min), and ultra-short-term, assessed using the time domain, frequency domain, and non-linear measurements. Time-domain indices (Table 1) measure variability in interbeat intervals (IBI).

Table 1. The time-domain measures of HRV.

Parameter	Unit	Description
SDNN	ms	Standard deviation of NN intervals
SDRR	ms	Standard deviation of RR intervals
SDANN	ms	Standard deviation of the average NN intervals for each 5 min segment of a 24 h HRV recording
SDNN index	ms	Mean of standard deviation of all the NN intervals for each 5 min segment of a 24h HRV recording
pNN50	%	Percentage of successive RR intervals that differ by more than 50 ms
HR Max-HR Min	bpm	Mean difference between the highest and lowest HR during each respiratory cycle
RMSSD	ms	Root mean square of successive RR interval differences
HRV triangular index		Integral of the density of the RR interval histogram divided by its height
TINN	ms	Baseline width of the RR interval histogram

NN intervals: interbeat intervals from which artifacts have been removed; RR interval: interbeat intervals between all successive heartbeats; Interbeat interval: time interval between successive heartbeats.

Frequency-domain measurements predict signal distribution across frequency bands, with HR vacillation categorized into Ultra-Low-Frequency, Very-Low-Frequency, Low-Frequency, and High-Frequency bands by the Task Force of the European Society of Cardiology and North American Society of Pacing and Electrophysiology (1996). Activity in these bands correlates with parasympathetic nervous system activity, expressed as “power” (EHRV, 2022). Non-linear measurement, assessing time-series unpredictability (Shaffer & Ginsberg, 2017), often employs DFA (detrended fluctuation analysis) to elucidate the non-linearity of HR variation through short-term fractal scaling exponent (Germán-Salló & Germán-Salló, 2016). HRV is one of the main outcomes in the present study that was chosen due to its characteristics that predict many health effects. Such as cardiovascular activity (Held et al., 2021), fibromyalgia (Kang et al., 2016), obesity and asthma (Lehrer & Gevirtz, 2004), chronic brain injury (Kim et al., 2013), major depressive disorder (Hartogs et al. 2017), PTSD (Schuman & Killan, 2018), and many more.

The most reliable and accurate HRV measurement used as the gold standard is ECG (Electrocardiogram). However, in order to measure it directly before and after intervention it needs alternative tools that are able to provide reports instantly. There are many digital devices which currently available commercially. Some advanced brands that have been studied are Fitbit, Apple Watch, Garmin, Galaxy Fit, and others that are able to collect data on physiological parameters such as heart rate, steps, energy expenditure, sleep duration, stress level, and others. Some more highly advanced devices are able to measure blood

pressure, blood glucose, and heart rate variability.

Studies have been conducted to test the reliability and validity of those devices in different settings. For instance, a systematic review from Fuller et al. (2020) compiled 158 publications with different commercial devices, such as Fitbit, Apple Watch, and Samsung, found that step count was able to predict accurately in all brands. HR was more viable for the Apple Watch and Garmin brands. A cross-sectional study by Chandrasekaran et al. (2021) indicates a significant positive association between self-efficacy, health status, demographic factors, and the use of wearable devices. Furthermore, a profound but small association between perceived stress and HRV in a laboratory setting was proven by Martinez et al. (2022). However, the association fell off in a real-life setting. This finding suggests the HRV signal obtained from wearables might be less effective in predicting perceived stress when individuals are in natural settings compared to the controlled settings. Viewed through an evolutionary lens, where humans instinctively focus on patterns signifying peril or safety (Katcher & Wilkins, 1993), the natural visual and acoustic settings in forests, regarded as restorative environments, are expected to convey cues of safety or a harmonious world devoid of threats. This, in turn, should enable individuals to regulate their mental states and reduce stress-related behaviors (Andringa & Lanser, 2013). These findings contribute to the understanding of earlier research, indicating that while the majority of biodiversity-related FES positively impact people, certain associations may be negative, highlighting the intricate and multifaceted mechanisms at play (Schwarz et al., 2017). It is worth noting that existing studies have predominantly occurred in controlled laboratory conditions, emphasizing the pressing need for more field studies, particularly concerning HRV measures.

2.5.2 Endocrine function

The endocrine system forms a complicated network of glands and organs that produce and discharge hormones. These chemical messengers serve as regulators for diverse physiological functions within the body; one of them is to respond to both internal and external stimuli. A biomarker or biological marker constitutes an objective and dynamic measure that furnishes valuable insights into the cellular or organismal state at a specific point. Functioning as a discerning indicator of health status, biomarkers serve as a sophisticated alert system (NIEHS, 2021). Among the plethora of biological markers illuminating the intricate mechanisms of stress response, cortisol emerges prominently. This steroid hormone, perceptible in diverse biological substrates including blood, saliva, urine,

hair, or sweat, assumes the role of a quintessential biomarker, providing a window into the orchestrated activity of the hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis. Cortisol, a glucocorticoid hormone emanating from the adrenal cortex via the HPA axis, is colloquially known as “stress hormone”. Its concentration exhibits a discernible surge in moments of heightened stress. Steroid hormones, a class synthesized endogenously from cholesterol, collectively regulate a myriad of physiological functions within the body. These functions cover a wide range, from carefully regulating metabolism and coordinating inflammatory responses to overseeing immune function and managing the subtle complexities of the stress response (Konkel, 2018; Thau et al., 2021).

In response to stress, the body initiates a primary mechanism triggered by internal and external stressors. The body processes the stress-related information and generates a response commensurate with the perceived threat level, whereby the amygdala, a key brain region, signals the brain stem to release sympathetic adrenergic catecholamines, namely, epinephrine and norepinephrine (Tsigos & Chrousos, 2002). These neurotransmitters, upon entering the bloodstream, prompt a series of physiological changes. They elevate heart rate, increase blood pressure, and enhance respiration. Simultaneously, there is vasoconstriction in arterioles, prompting the stimulation of sweat secretion and pupillary dilation (Vinik et al., 2011). This short-term sympathetic response has an impact on immune function. Additionally, mineralocorticoids, such as aldosterone, are produced. These regulatory agents play a role in the re-absorption of water and sodium in the kidneys. Moreover, they regulate the active secretion of potassium in the principal cells of the cortical collecting tubule and protons via proton ATPase in the luminal membrane of the intercalated cells of the collecting tubule. This intricate regulation results in an increase in blood pressure and blood volume (Lee et al., 2015).

Salivary cortisol is widely recognized as a crucial indicator of acute stress. Nevertheless, cortisol levels in saliva exhibit a diurnal pattern, peaking upon waking, experiencing a notable surge of approximately 50-60% within the first 30-40 minutes after awakening, followed by a sharp decline in the subsequent hours. Subsequently, cortisol gradually decreases until reaching a nadir function around bedtime (Adam et al., 2017). This dynamic pattern can be effectively addressed with appropriate research methodologies. Additionally, this study also includes the measurement of alpha-amylase, a salivary enzyme. Alpha-amylase responds to stress through sympathetic activation. Some evidence suggests that increased salivary alpha-amylase activity is associated with psychosocial stress (Petrankova et al., 2015), anxiety (Santos et al., 2021), depression (Izáková et al., 2020), and

mild cognitive impairment (Yamane et al., 2023). Hair cortisol is a novel, non-invasive biomarker that offers a feasible method for chronic stress measurement was also the main outcome. It captures the HPA axis activity retrospectively. Every one level of cortisol extracted from one centimeter of hair from the scalp indicates a previous one month of cortisol secretion. The optimum proximal to obtain long-term stress is a 3 cm segment of hair, providing insights into systemic cortisol exposure over a three-month period (Nafisa et al., 2021), beyond that the ability to predict chronic stress is no longer accurate as cortisol concentration declines due to leaching effects (Kirschbaum et al., 2009; Gow et al., 2010).

2.5.3 Cognitive function

Cognitive problems are widespread among older individuals, and determining their causes can be problematic, as these issues may stem from factors like forgetfulness, depression, normal aging, or other unidentified conditions (Medalia et al., 2002). Cognitive function refers to the mental capabilities and thinking skills that enable individuals to perceive, acquire, comprehend, and respond to information from their surroundings (Medalia et al., 2002; Kiel, 2014). The exploration of specific cognitive domains or pathways in the brain linked to certain psychological disease processes is known as neurocognitive function (Sharafkhaneh & Grogan, 2015). According to Sachdev et al. (2014), there are 6 key domains in the neurocognitive domains that are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The neurocognitive domains based on DSM-5. Adapted from Sachdev et al. (2014)

People with schizophrenia, bipolar, and affective disorders tend to get a mental illness that induces a decrease in cognitive function. According to Kiosses (2005), severe depression and impairment in the specific cognitive domain are associated with instrumental activities of daily living (IADI), including fatigue in places of walking distance, going shopping for groceries, preparing own meals, doing housework, doing handyman work, laundry, taking medicine, and managing money. Poor performance on neurocognitive tasks is associated with poor performance in community functioning, psychosocial skill acquisition, and social problem-solving (Mohamed et al., 2008). Plenty of cognitive assessment tools have been used by clinicians, such as Mini Mental Status Exam (MMSE), Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA), Trail Making Test (TMT), etc. Along with a health history, a physical exam and appropriate laboratory assessment can establish the right diagnosis (Petersen, 2016; Finney et al., 2016; Gonzalez Kelso & Tadi, 2022).

2.5.4 Quality of life

Quality of life (QoL) is paramount to study in order to help society understand better how health, diseases, and treatment impact the quality of life (ISOQOL, n.d.). Quality of life is the individual perception of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards, and concerns (Martin & Amin, 2008). modeled how the elderly experience quality of life (Figure 4). It is categorized into four main domains, which contain sub-domains (Anchorage to life, conditions governing one's life, satisfied body and mind, and access to significant relations).

Figure 4. Tentative model of older adults' experience of quality of life. Adapted from Borglin et al. (2005).

Myriad measurement tools have been standardized in order to assess the quality of life for the elderly population. Namely, OPQOL (Older People's Quality of Life Questionnaire), CASP-19 (Control, Autonomy, Self-Realization, and Pleasure), WHOQOL (World Health Organization Quality of Life), DQOL (Dementia Quality of Life), QUALID (Quality of Life in Late-Stage Dementia), LTC-QOL (Long Term Care Quality of Life), SF-36 (36-Item Short Form Health Survey), etc (Siette et al., 2021). Understanding target group characteristics, settings, and interest are essential in order to judge which instrument would suit the research best.

3. STUDY OBJECTIVES

3.1 Study justification

Alongside the trend of urbanization, population growth, and international migration, a demographic shift is also marked by the increase of the aging population all across the world (UNDESA, 2019). This trend leads to a complex challenge either for the elderly or the government body, mainly the issue concerning mental health, which affects the overall quality of life in later life. As a result, the interest in nature- and forest-based intervention and therapy has been growing fast. It has been shown to improve mental well-being (Joschko et al., 2023), reduce psychological distress (Hyvönen et al., 2022), improve mood and mindfulness (Poulsen et al., 2016; Sidenius et al., 2017), improve concentration and attention (Weir, 2020), social connectivity (Leavell et al., 2019), promote physical activities (Howarth et al., 2020), as well as many other benefits.

Leaning on the available evidence and the identified gaps in the existing knowledge, our study was designed to address the pressing need to better understand how nature-based interventions, particularly in forests, specifically impact the health of older adults. Our research centered on individual walking within both managed and unmanaged woodland settings (with urban environment serving as the control). Participants were deliberately exposed to the diverse array of biological, physical, and other biophilia elements of nature, all within a travel distance of 3 to 25 minutes by car, repeated over the course of one month (8 interventions). The outcome variables under scrutiny encompassed physiological metrics, specifically Heart Rate Variability (HRV), and various psychological states denoted by Salivary Cortisol Concentration (SCC), Salivary Alpha-Amylase (SAA), and Hair Cortisol Concentration (HCC). Additionally, cognitive function and quality of life in the older adult cohort were integral facets of our investigation.

3.2 Study aims

Focusing on physiological and psychological responses, especially chronic stress assessment using innovative methods like hair cortisol measurement, it aimed to fill some crucial gaps in knowledge. Through real-time monitoring devices like heart rate variability (HRV), this study strives to unique produce new insights into these interventions' effects on the well-being of older adults. Ultimately, this research aimed to enhance older adults' overall health and quality of life, offering practical strategies for individuals, forest owners,

administrators, and managers, as well as public health policy-makers to leverage nature-based therapies in forest settings for the well-being of elderly population.

3.3 Objective and hypothesis

The main aim of this dissertation is to determine and compare the restoration effects of several individual walks in forest and urban environments, evenly distributed during one-month intervention period, on physiological and psychological responses, cognitive function, and quality of life of older adults.

There were six specific objectives:

- a) To descriptively provide an objective measure of neighborhood greenness of study participants;
- b) To assess changes in heart rate variability pre- to post-walks in both environments and to investigate the influence of air temperature on HRV and environment interaction;
- c) To investigate changes in salivary cortisol concentration, salivary amylase concentration, and hair cortisol concentration following the intervention in both environments;
- d) To examine and analyze cognitive performance between and within groups' difference;
- e) To investigate changes in quality-of-life in both environments and to evaluate whether quality-of-life components improved, stagnant, or deteriorated post-intervention;
- f) To establish whether positive outcomes from forest intervention would occur in forests unadjusted for recreational and restorative purposes;

The research hypotheses were as follows:

- a) Both forest and urban interventions are expected to lead to a reduction in stress levels and improvement in cognitive functions and quality of life;
- b) Forest walks are anticipated to be more effective than urban walks in reducing stress, enhancing cognitive flexibility, and improving overall quality of life;
- c) Intervention effect size on cognitive functions is greater than on stress reductions;
- d) One or more environmental factors act as moderators of the presumed intervention effects on older adults;
- e) Unmanaged forests provide desired mental health benefits on a level at least comparable to forests managed for recreation and restoration;

4. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study was conducted from the 1st to the 31st of October 2021, during a period without heatwaves or sub-zero daily temperatures. The selected time period was between two COVID-19 pandemic waves when the pandemic related measures were eased, but social interaction had to be kept at a minimum.

4.1 Participants

The study was conducted on a sample consisting of fifty-four older adults (60 years of age and older) living in the district of Zvolen, a town located in one of the urbanized and industrialized Slovak regions, with a population of 43 thousand citizens. The participants were recruited in collaboration with the municipal social and older adult welfare authorities from June to August 2021. To be enrolled in the study, participants had to meet the inclusion criteria: (1) age of 60+, (2) vaccinated from COVID-19, (3) being able to walk independently, and (4) willing to participate in a one-month intervention. The exclusion criteria were: (5) staying in institutional care, (6) prescribed antidepressant drugs. Seventy-four older adults took part on the orientation day, and 54 of them met the criteria. A professional administrator was hired to aid participants in scheduling their visits as well as provide instructions based on developed protocols. In addition, eight field assistants were recruited and trained in necessary guidance and data collection. The minimum sample size of 52 was calculated with GPower 3.1 (Faul et al., 2007; Faul et al., 2009) with an estimated effect size medium (Cohen's d : 0.5) assuming significance level: 0.05, and power: 0.80 (Bratman et al., 2015; Koselka et al., 2019; Cohen, 1988). The final sample size was 54, with two additional (27 in each group) registered for a two-treatment parallel design study. Since only two participants dropped out due to a schedule conflict and an accident at home, and therefore a per-protocol analysis was carried out.

4.2 Study design and procedure

The study was based on a randomized, parallel intervention design (Figure 5). Before starting the intervention, all subjects signed the informed consent form. Study participants were randomly assigned into the forest (intervention) and urban (active control) groups with a ratio of 1:1 through the web-based research randomizer (www.randomizer.org). Blinding from the specific research questions was conducted for participants and the research assistants. Four to two days prior to the intervention, the baseline data were collected, and

measurements were taken. The participants filled out the baseline questionnaire, and afterward, research assistants administered TMT and SF-36 questionnaires to each individual. For salivary marker, participants were asked to do it based on the provided protocols. Meanwhile, hair cortisol was collected by the team from the Slovak Academy of Science. Finally, the participants were provided with and instructed to use Garmin Venu Sq, consumer wrist-worn fitness tracking devices using photoplethysmography sensors, for 24 h a day during the whole intervention period (endline).

Figure 5. Design and research timeline of the randomized parallel intervention.

4.3 Intervention sites

There were three urban and three forest intervention localities, and each participant completed a minimum of two interventions in each of them according to their assignment to the urban or forest group. Multiple locations were selected to avoid boredom and fatigue. At the end, the aggregated means of the main effect of forest and urban environment were used.

The localities were selected based on topographic data and field reconnaissance to ensure comfortable walkability on relatively even surfaces (trails, pavement) with a max. 3° inclination to avoid physical exertion and acceptable driving times from participants' addresses, similar for both urban and forest localities and groups (5–25 minutes). The study was conducted in the Central Slovakia. For urban sites, two major towns (Banská Bystrica, Zvolen) were selected. Two main walking spots were established in Zvolen and one in Banská Bystrica (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Walking routes in the urban sites: (A) Zvolen; (B) Banská Bystrica.

The forest sites featured species and structural diversity: Mláčik (48.664°, 19.026°) – a non-managed, mixed fir-beech-spruce old-growth forest; Stráže (48.579°, 19.095°) – a beech-oak-hornbeam forest subject to shelterwood management; and Sliač (48.611°, 19.160°) – a mixed pine-hornbeam-spruce forest surrounding a spa complex (Figure 7). The walking pathways in each site were around one kilometer in length. The average air temperatures for October 2021 were obtained from the main weather station of the Slovak Hydrometeorological Institute, Bratislava, in Sliač, and several nearby stations operated by the National Forestry Centre, Zvolen, and the Technical University in Zvolen. The air temperatures were as follows: Sliač – 12.1 °C, Stráže – 11.0 °C, Mláčik – 9.5 °C, Banská Bystrica – 12.0 °C, and Zvolen – 12.5 °C. The average minimum temperature between 9:00 a.m. and 4:00 p.m. in Sliač declined from 9.2 °C during the first period (walks 1–4) to 6.4 °C during the second period (walks 5–8) of the intervention.

Figure 7. The interiors of the three forest intervention localities: A – Mláčik, a fir-beech-spruce natural forest. B – Stráže, a peri-urban beech-hornbeam forest. C – Sliach, a mixed pine-hornbeam-spruce forest. The pictures were taken in October 2021, when the experiment was conducted.

Walking and resting scenes during the experiment in forest and urban environment are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Walking and resting in forest and urban environment.

4.4 Measured variables

4.4.1 Heart rate variability

The HRV was measured through Garmin Venu Sq, a consumer wrist-worn tracking device equipped with a PPG sensor (Garmin, n.d.), during 3-minute windows before and after each of the eight interventions. Many researchers used smart watch devices to gather the long-term HRV data from participants in real-life settings in order to provide valuable inputs on how day to day basis stressors and lifestyle drivers impact autonomic nervous system regulation. Consumer wrist-worn fitness tracking devices with photoplethysmography (PPG)

sensors have been increasingly used to measure HRV in outdoor environment research (Natarajan et al., 2020; Evenson & Spade, 2020). Binary classification of HRV changes (e.g., HRV increase detected vs. not) is sometimes used in ecological momentary assessment research (Schwerdtfeger & Rominger, 2021). Since the Garmin Venu Sq does not have the HRV feature built into it by default, we used TestHrv, a custom Garmin Connect application (Retty, 2022) available from Garmin Conenct IQ, a platform for developers to build applications and features that engage and integrate with Garmin wearable devices. TestHrv measurement illustration display is shown below (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Illustration of TestHrv measurement using Garmin Venu Sq.

TestHrv reports HRV features such as RMSSD, pNN20, pNN50, beat-to-beat interval, HRV successive differences, SDRR, HRV 30 sec window, and HR. Among all of these features, RMSSD was chosen as it has been the most reported predictor for stress (Immanuel et al., 2023) and anxious depression (Kircanski et al., 2019), and provides a reliable metric of vagal activity (Cosmo et al., 2022). TestHrv measures HRV in a 3-minute representing RMSSD ultra-short-term HRV, which has been a good surrogate method to assess trends in

HRV (Baek et al., 2015), and has predicted mental stress in healthy people (Castaldo et al., 2015). We measured HRV during rest five minutes after the arrival at the sites and five minutes after the slow walking. HRV values from walks during which a participant reported strong anxiety or acute stress due to biophobia were not included in the analysis. The post-to pre-walk HRV difference (Δ HRV) was analyzed as an interval variable and a nominal variable in the binarized form (Δ HRV > 0, Δ HRV \leq 0). The Garmin Venu Sq provides a range of health and fitness metrics like heart rate, sleep tracking, activity tracking, GPS tracking, SpO2 (blood oxygen saturation), body battery, and stress tracking, etc. Nevertheless, we were specifically interested in a subset of these metrics, as outlined below:

Heart Rate (HR)

The heart rate feature in most fitness smartwatches provides continuous HR monitoring throughout the day. It allows users to track their heart rate during rest and do various activities features innate of Garmin Venu Sq such as walking, running, treadmill, yoga, cycling and many others. For older adults (aged 60+), the reference value of real-world heart rate is \leq 95 bpm (Avram et al., 2019).

Sleep tracking

Sleep tracking feature allows the users to monitor their sleep duration, light and deep sleep, and rapid-eyed movement sleep, which indicate the overall sleep quality. Garmin specifies that deep sleep range is between 13–23% of sleep duration, no specific range for light sleep, rapid eye movement between 20–25% of sleep duration. Sleep duration for older adults is between 7 to 9 hours each night (NIH, 2020). A device with activity tracking records sleep during regular sleep hours but only considers additional rest periods as naps in the total sleep time if the device is in sleep mode. These separate rest periods will not be included in the sleep graph. When setting up the device, users are asked to input their regular sleep hours. This information is used to calculate sleep time for the graph in the sleep widget (both on the website and mobile app) or the complete sleep page. When the watch is in sleep mode, either at night or during extra rest periods like naps, it uses this input to determine the total sleep time. Naps will be displayed separately on the full "SLEEP" page for that day (e.g., Total sleep: 8 hours + 30 min Nap).

Activity tracking

Activity tracking features provide a wide range of fitness activities and can provide

information on how many steps are taken, distance traveled, calories burned, and GPS tracking.

Stress tracking

The stress tracking feature uses an undisclosed heart rate variability algorithm and then transforms it into stress levels with a range from 0 as no stress to 100, indicating very high stress.

Step count

The step function creates a daily step target based on the previous activity, and throughout the day, the watch displays the advancement toward reaching this daily goal. Research has recommended that in order to achieve healthy aging, older adults have to perform at least 150 minutes of moderate-intensity physical activity per week (e.g., 30 minutes a day, 5 days a week), or 75 minutes a week with vigorous intensity activity including hiking, jogging, or running. Besides, it is also encouraged to perform activities that strengthen muscles for at least 2 days a week as well as activities that are important for balance improvement, for instance, standing on one foot (CDC, 2023). When it converts to step count, Marshall et al. (2009) indicated 3000 steps in 30 minutes. For many years, the widely endorsed target for optimal health benefits has been 10 000 steps per day, as advocated by various studies (Lee et al., 2019; Torjesen, 2019). However, recent findings propose that striving for a range of 8000 to 10 000 steps daily can significantly decrease the risk of cardiovascular disease, diabetes, dementia, and premature death. The revised goal is more achievable than the traditionally promoted 10 000 steps per day, as indicated by studies such as Paluch et al. (2022), Del Pozo Cruz et al. (2022), Ballin et al. (2020), and Lee et al. (2019b).

Respiration

Respiration feature gauges breaths per minute (brpm). At rest, respiration rates generally fall within the range of 12–20 breaths per minute, while they may rise to approximately 40–50 breaths per minute during vigorous physical activity. The elevated respiration rate during intense exercise is a response to the heightened need for oxygen to support aerobic energy production.

Although we asked participants to wear this device all day to experience real-life settings, including when sleeping, the above metrics we were interested in were not significantly different between groups and were not contributing to our outcome measures. Hence, we did not include it in any further analysis¹. However, we provide their basic descriptive statistics in the Annex 1 Table S1.

4.4.2 Salivary cortisol and alpha-amylase concentration

Salivary steroids, such as cortisol, are well-known markers of acute stress responses in humans (Ježová & Hlaváčová, 2008). Saliva sample collection is quite straightforward to conduct by self-administered procedure. Besides demonstrating it in front of participants, we also provided the written protocols therewith the toolkits. Therefore, the participants would have no issues regarding memory. Saliva samples were taken twice on the first day of baseline measurement. The tubes were labeled with A (15 minutes after waking in the morning) and B (after walking) and twice at the endline measurements (labeled C and D as the same conditions as baseline). After collecting morning saliva, participants kept it in their refrigerator before the taxi driver picked them up at the research settings. Collected saliva, then handed after walking activity and transferred into the university's fridge and kept at -20°C . After the intervention period was completed, it was then transported to a specialized lab with a cold chain to be further assessed.

Saliva samples were collected into saliva sampling tubes (Salivette® device; Sarstedt). The subjects were asked to gently chew the cotton roll from the sampling tube for 1 min. Salivettes were stored at -20°C until analyzed. Concentrations of cortisol in saliva were determined using a commercially available enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (IBL International, Germany). The intra- and inter-assay coefficients of variation were 2.9% and 5.0%, respectively. Meanwhile, the salivary alpha-amylase was measured by a commercial kinetic reaction assay (Salimetrics, Suffolk, UK). The coefficient of intra- and inter-assay variation was 6.7% and 3.6%, respectively).

The reference value for salivary cortisol concentration can vary based on laboratory methods, population characteristics, and study designs. Additionally, salivary cortisol levels are influenced by circadian rhythm, decreasing throughout the day. A specific study focusing on three age groups (40–59 years old, 60–69 years old, and ≥ 70 years old) found that the

¹ It's noteworthy that, despite our extensive exploration, no discernible impact or contribution was observed from behavioral factors or conditions, particularly for physical activity and sleep, throughout the course of this study.

baseline salivary cortisol concentration at 8 am was 4.39 nmol/l, with a maximum cortisol change relative to baseline of 1.32. Specifically for male elderly, the salivary cortisol was 5.14 nmol/l at baseline, then dropped to 1.39 nmol/l at maximum. Meanwhile, female elders were 3.84 nmol/l, and the peak was 1.99 nmol/l (Nicolson et al., 1997).

For salivary alpha-amylase, in the context of stressors (speech task and arithmetic task in front of an audience), older adults aged 59–61 years reported alpha-amylase levels ranging from 7 to 140 U/ml, with a mean of 46.6 U/ml measured immediately before, and after 10 and 20 minutes (Strahler et al., 2010). It's essential to recognize that these studies were conducted in a different setting than the present study, and the provided references help to compare existing literature in regards cortisol and alpha amylase value as stress-related responses.

4.4.3 Hair cortisol concentration

The biological stress-related hormones such as cortisol are an effective proxy for long-term stress (Wright et al., 2015), and it is considered novel (Balagová & Ježová, 2018). The analysis used the most proximal 1 cm of hair (25 mg), which enables retrospectively measuring a cumulative amount of cortisol secretion during the last one month. Steroid hormone cortisol was extracted from hair using the methodology described by Balagová & Ježová (2018). Hair is carefully cut with fine scissors as close as possible to the scalp from a posterior vertex position. Then, it was placed in the 50 ml Falcon tube and washed 3 times with 5 ml aliquots of isopropanol and allowed to dry for at least 12 hours. Afterward, it was pulverized with an ULTRA-TURRAX Tube Drive (IKA Works, Inc., Wilmington, NC). The hair powder was eluted with 2 ml of methanol. After centrifugation, 1 ml of methanol was transferred into a new glass tube and evaporated at 50 °C in a water bath. The residue was diluted with phosphate-buffer saline. Cortisol concentrations in hair extracts were measured by the Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) kit (IBL International, Germany). The intra- and inter-assay coefficients of variation were 2.9% and 5.0%, respectively. Hair for hair cortisol measurement could not be collected only from few subjects due to drop-out owing to health issues, unwillingness to provide the sample during the endline measurement, and unsuitable timing. They were excluded from further analysis, which was carried out at a specialized laboratory.

The reference value for hair cortisol concentration is rare in older adults' context since it varies also according to age, sex, population characteristics, and laboratory unit used. However, we found some studies which could be used as a reference, at least until the present

time, such as Gonzalez et al. (2019), who assessed the hair cortisol level of 286 individuals measured using an automated chemoluminescent immunoassay analyzer and found median reference of hair cortisol concentration in healthy individuals (mean age of men was 41 years and women were 45 years) was 55 pg/mg hair, with a range of 40–128 pg/mg (2.5–97.5 percentile) for low stressed people, while the median concentration for stressed individuals ranged from 182 to 520 pg/mg. In the context of older adults aged over 50 years old, three studies have documented that the mean average hair cortisol concentration varied between 21.0 and 40.5 picograms per milligram (Manenschijn et al., 2013; Feller et al., 2014; Pulpulos et al., 2014).

4.4.4 Cognitive function

The Trail Making Test (TMT-A and TMT-B) was administered to assess the cognitive performance of older adults before and after the intervention. TMT A and B tests are widely used neuropsychological tests that assess cognitive function, particularly in the domains of attention, processing speed, and executive functions (Ciolek & Lee, 2020). We used the validated Slovak TMT version that was earlier used to establish normative data for the adult Slovak population (Málišová et al., 2021). For TMT A, participants are instructed to swiftly draw lines connecting circled numbers in sequential order (for example, 1-2-3 until 25). For TMT B, participants are directed to draw lines connecting circled numbers and letters in an alternating pattern of numeric and alphabetic sequences to rapidly as fast as possible (for example, 1-A-2-B until 12-L). The cut-off time of 300 seconds was applied to discontinue the test administration (Bowie & Harvey, 2006; Reitan, 1956), and the respective cases were not used in further analysis. The TMT B-A values were calculated as differences between TMT-B and TMT-A scores, both at baseline and endline.

The typical completion time for TMT-A is 29 seconds, and a below-average score is considered to be more than 78 seconds. As for TMT-B, an average completion time is approximately 75 seconds, and a below-average score is greater than 273 seconds. Norms for these tests have been determined taking into account factors such as age and school attainment (Tombaugh, 2004). Above the average scores, TMT has been associated with behavioral and psychological symptoms of dementia in mild cognitive impairment and Alzheimer's disease (Toda et al., 2021).

4.4.5 Quality of Life

We used the standardized Slovak version of the 36-item Sort-Form Health Survey (SF-36) to determine health-related quality of life. SF-36 is a set of genetic, coherent, and easily administered quality-of-life measures. SF-36 consists of two dimensions: a physical dimension, which is represented by Physical Component Summary (PCS), and a mental dimension, which is represented by Mental Component Summary (PMS). It elaborates eight health scales, namely, physical functioning (PF), role physical (RP), bodily pain (BP), general health (GH), social functioning (SF), role emotional (RE), and mental health (MH) or emotional well-being (Hays, 1994). This survey was conducted immediately before the beginning and after the end of the intervention. The details of the reference mean and score interpretation are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. SF-36 reference mean and score interpretation based on Ware and Sherbourne (1992)

SF-36 components	Reference mean	Low	High
Physical functioning	70.61	limited a lot in performing all physical activities including bathing or dressing due to health	Performs all types of physical activities including the most vigorous without limitation due to health
Role functioning physical	52.97	Problems with work or other daily activities as a result of physical health	no problems with work or other daily activities as a result of physical health
Pain	70.77	Very severe and extremely limiting pain	No pain or limitation due to pain
Role functioning emotional	65.78	Problems with work or other daily activities as a result of emotional problems	no problems with work or other daily activities as a result emotional problems
Energy	52.15	Feels tired and worn out all of the time	feels full of pep and energy all of the time
Social functioning	78.77	Extreme and frequent interference with normal social activities due to physical or emotional problems	Performs normal social activities without interference due to physical or emotional problems
Emotional well-being	70.38	Feeling of nervousness and depression all of the time	Feels peacefull, happy, and calm all of the time
General health	56.99	Evaluates personal health as poor and believes it is likely to get worse	Evaluates personal health as excellent

4.5 Ethical consideration

The study was approved by the Independent Ethical Committee of the Banská Bystrica Self-Governing Region (BBSK) for Biomedical Research, registration No. 37828100.

4.6 Statistical analysis

Baseline characteristics were analyzed using the chi-square test for categorical variables and the Student's *t*-test for continuous variables. Potential outliers identified by the Dixon test ($p < 0.01$) were regarded in further analyses. Two-way repeated measures ANOVA was conducted to analyze differences in TMT-A, TMT-B, and TMT B-A scores between baseline and endline (within-subjects factor), as well as between forest and urban interventions (between-subjects factor). This analysis also aimed to determine whether an interaction between these two factors had an effect on the dependent variable. The Student's *t*-test for independent samples was used to compare the angular coefficients m representing the baseline to endline slopes of changes specifically for TMT B-A in the forest and urban groups. Each value of m was calculated from the corresponding equation in the slope-intercept form $y = mx + b$ (Izáková et al., 2020). The differences between post- and pre-walk HRV values in both environments, and between the forest and urban groups were assessed through the paired samples and independent samples *t*-test, respectively. Moderation analysis relying on the Johnson-Neyman technique was employed to establish whether air temperature modulated the relationship between Δ HRV and the environment, as well as the modulation region of significance. The Johnson-Neyman Technique is a statistical approach used in moderation analysis, particularly in ANOVA or regression models. It helps identify significant regions in the interaction between two continuous variables. It is beneficial in scenarios where researchers want to understand how a third continuous variable moderates the relationship between the predictor variable and an outcome variable. This technique is especially useful for avoiding dichotomization of the moderator variable, providing a graphical representation of significance regions, and understanding conditional effects in complex statistical models. It offers a nuanced understanding of moderation effects by pinpointing specific values of the moderator that influence the significance of the interaction effect (Montoya, 2018).

The assessment of binarized Δ HRV changes (Δ HRV > 0 vs. Δ HRV ≤ 0) expressed as proportions of positive Δ HRV cases relative to all measurements (N) in a given cell was conducted using a chi-square contingency table. The phi (ϕ), partial eta-squared (η^2_p), and Cohen's d coefficients were used to evaluate effect sizes in the respective statistical tests.

The results were considered statistically significant when $p < 0.05$. HRV and cognitive function were performed with IBM SPSS statistics software for macOS (version 28, IBM Corp, Armonk, NY, USA).

For biomarkers, we reported their original mean and confidence interval. Meanwhile, log-transformed for these outcomes was computed due to positively skewed data for further analysis. We run a linear mixed-effect model to determine whether the biomarker outcomes depend on the environment, time, and sub-time while taking into account the individual variation of the participants. A Linear Mixed Effects Model (LMM), also referred to as a Mixed Effects Model or Hierarchical Linear Model (HLM), is a statistical approach that combines fixed effects and random effects to analyze data with repeated measures or hierarchical structures. It extends traditional linear regression models by considering both population-level trends (fixed effects) and individual or group-specific deviations from these trends (random effects). The model is particularly useful for studying correlated or clustered data, repeated measures, and nested structures. Key components include fixed effects representing average relationships, random effects capturing unexplained variability within groups, and grouping variables defining the hierarchical structure of the data (Magezi, 2015; UCLA, n.d.).

We modeled Environment (urban and forest), Time (baseline and endline), and Sub-time (morning and after walking) to act as the categorical fixed factors, and Participants were the random factors. The log-transformed cortisol concentration, salivary cortisol concentration, and salivary alpha-amylase were included in the model as outcome variables. All fixed effects were kept in the model regardless of whether or not they had a significant impact on the outcome variables. For quality of life outcome, we first tested a Mann-Whitney U test to check out the difference between two environments with non-normally distributed data. We found no significant difference between forest and urban groups in this study. Therefore, we conducted a Wilcoxon signed rank test to look further at within-group comparisons before and after the intervention. A Chi-square test was applied to determine which components of quality of life underwent improved, constant, or deteriorated post of our intervention. The results were considered statistically significant when $p < 0.05$. Biomarkers and quality of life were analyzed using R software (Rstudio version 2022.12.0 Build 353).

5. RESULTS

5.1. Baseline characteristics and objective measure of the natural environment

Baseline characteristics of participants in the forest and urban groups and descriptive environmental indicators of their residential areas based on remote sensing analysis are depicted in Table 3. The characteristics and indicators were assessed using the chi-square test for categorical variables and Student's *t*-test for continuous variables. We assigned both females and males randomly into groups equally. The urban group has a younger age compared to the forest group, and the residential areas of the urban group members feature higher NDVI ($p < 0.01$). Other variables (BMI, marital status, education, tobacco/smoking status, number of chronic illnesses, drug intake, occupation, household income, tree canopy coverage, and distance to parks and forests) were similar in both groups. The details for objective measures of residential greenness are presented in Figure 10.

Table 3. Baseline characteristics of the participants.

Characteristics	Environment		Significance
	Forest ($N = 27$)	Urban ($N = 27$)	p, r
Sex, male (n (%))	10 (37)	10 (37)	1
Age in years *	72.3 (5.2)	69.7 (4.5)	0.055
BMI *	27.94 (4.5)	27.87 (4.4)	0.95
BMI Underweight (n (%))	4 (14)	4 (14)	0.17
BMI Overweight (n (%))	10 (37)	8 (29)	0.27
Marital status			
Married/partnership	15	18	0.57
Unmarried	1	0	1
Divorced	3	3	1
Widowed	8	6	0.75
Education			
Basic	0	3	0.23
Medium	17	11	0.17
High School	10	13	0.58
Tobacco/Smoking status			
Non-smoker	20	25	0.14
Ex-smoker	2	2	1
Current smoker	5	0	0.06
No. of chronic illness			
Has 1	11	13	0.78
Has >1	10	10	1
None	6	4	0.72
SES			
Employed	0	1	1
Entrepreneur	0	0	–
Retired	27	26	1
Disabled retired	0	0	–
Unemployed	0	0	–

Characteristics	Environment		Significance <i>p, r</i>
	Forest (<i>N</i> = 27)	Urban (<i>N</i> = 27)	
Others	0	0	–
Household Income (€)			
≤ 500	3	7	0.29
501–800	11	10	1
801–1500	13	8	0.26
>1500	0	2	0.47
COVID-19 History			
No	23	25	0.66
Yes	4	2	0.66
Natural Environment*			
NDVI	0.23 (0.07)	0.27 (0.08)	< 0.01 , 0.26
Tree canopy coverage (%)	5.07 (3.51)	7.02 (5.44)	0.13
Distance to park (m)	726.91 (1006.18)	1288.4 (1321.57)	0.08
Distance to forest (m)	644.2 (373.99)	515.1 (357.12)	0.20

NDVI – Normalized Difference Vegetation Index

* Mean (SD)

p – level of significance

r – effect size (where $p < 0.05$)

Figure 10. (A) Remote sensing analysis on normalized difference vegetation index within 300 m (mean 0.26), (B) Tree cover within 300 m (mean 3.48%), (C) Distance to forest (mean 576.68 m), (D) Distance to parks (mean 1025.65 m). Red dots represent participant residences. The arrows point to the near greenery, and their size indicates the distance in meters.

5.2 Heart rate variability

Both the forest and urban walks were associated with a significant pre- to post-walk HRV increase when calculated for the entire intervention period (walks 1–8) and analyzed through the paired samples *t*-test (Table 4). In terms of sub-periods, the differences between pre- to post-walk values were significant in the forest group for walks 1–4 and in the urban group for walks 5–8. An effect size of at least medium magnitude was observed only for the pre- to post-walk average Δ HRV in the forest group during the first sub-period (Cohen's $d = 0.70$). Also within that sub-period, the forest group exhibited a larger average pre- to post-walk HRV change compared to the urban group, as indicated by the results of the independent samples *t*-test ($p = 0.037$). The difference was accompanied by a small to medium effect size (Cohen's $d = 0.28$).

Table 4. Paired samples *t*-test of the differences between pre- and post-walk heart rate variability, and independent samples *t*-test of the differences between the forest and urban groups. Unit is in millisecond. Abbreviations: HRV – heart rate variability, CI – confidence intervals (only the significant), r – effect size. Bold font indicates statistical significance ($p < 0.05$).

Period	Group	Time	<i>N</i>	Mean HRV	SD	Δ HRV [95% CI]	df	<i>p</i>	Cohen's <i>d</i>
1	Forest	Pre-walk	105	36.39	16.18	6.0 [2.93, 9.43]	104	< 0.001	0.7
		Post-walk	105	41.77	19.21				
	Urban	Pre-walk	106	42.25	18.99	1.19	105	> 0.4	–
		Post-walk	106	43.44	19.77				
	Forest Urban	–	105 106	–	–	4.89 [0.30, 9.48]	209	0.037	0.28
2	Forest	Pre-walk	103	35.86	12.97	0.61	102	> 0.6	–
		Post-walk	103	36.47	14.22				
	Urban	Pre-walk	106	39.57	19.31	3.60 [0.55, 6.65]	105	0.021	0.45
		Post-walk	106	43.17	18.96				
	Forest Urban	–	103 106	–	–	–2.99	196	> 0.1	–
1 & 2	Forest	Pre-walk	208	39.15	16.59	3.37 [1.30, 5.45]	207	0.002	0.45
		Post-walk	208	35.77	15.20				
	Urban	Pre-walk	212	43.30	19.50	2.39 [0.20, 4.58]	211	0.032	0.30
		Post-walk	212	40.91	18.98				
	Forest Urban	–	208 212	–	–	0.98	417	> 0.5	–

The opposite relationships between Δ HRV and environment during the first vs. the second sub-periods raised the possibility that the hypothesized modulation through an ambient factor, namely temperature, which decreased by 2.8 °C between the first and the second period, was at play. The modulating effect of air temperature by way of its interaction with the environment was identified by the Johnson-Neyman technique ($R^2 = 0.05$, $b = 2.56$,

CI [0.35, 4.77], $t = 2.33$, $t_{crit} = 2.03$, $p = 0.024$). This result indicates that after adjusting for the interaction, the average Δ HRV in the forest group was 2.56 ms higher than in the urban group. The interaction plot in Figure 11 (A) shows that as temperature decreased, Δ HRV also decreased in the forest settings and increased in the urban settings. However, this modulation was statistically significant only within the Johnson-Neyman region of significance, approximately below 9.9 °C ($p = 0.05$), as shown in Figure 11 (B). Remarkably, the partial overlap between the interaction's region of significance and the decline in average 9:00 a.m. to 4:00 p.m. air temperature from 9.2°C in the first period to 6.4°C in the second period resulted in the mutual convergence of Δ HRV in the two environments toward the second sub-period.

Figure 11. (A) Influence of the interaction between environment and temperature on HRV (RMSSD) change; (B) Johnson-Neyman plot for the effect of environment on HRV (RMSSD) change modulated by temperature within the region of significance.

Notably, the full chi-square contingency table (Table 5) and the proportions of binarized Δ HRV (Δ HRV > 0 vs. N) according to environment (Table 6) mirror the results from the analysis of Δ HRV as an interval variable (Table 4). The chi-square test of the difference in proportions with time as the layering variable showed a directional relationship between the binarized Δ HRV and environment during the first sub-period. In other words, the number of cases with increased HRV relative to N tended to be higher in the forest group than in the urban group. Importantly, these results indicate that both interventions and modulation through air temperature affected the majority of participants in the two groups.

Table 5. Chi-square contingency table with the numbers of cases of increased and decreased HRV (Δ HRV > 0, Δ HRV \leq 0, respectively) in the forest and urban groups during the intervention sub-periods (walks 1–4 and 5–8) and for the whole intervention period (walks 1–8).

Group	Intervention period 1		Intervention period 2		Whole intervention	
	Δ HRV > 0	Δ HRV \leq 0	Δ HRV > 0	Δ HRV \leq 0	Δ HRV > 0	Δ HRV \leq 0
Forest	69	36	58	45	127	81
Urban	55	51	63	43	118	94

Table 6. The chi-square test of the proportions of cases with positive pre- to post-walk heart rate variability change (Δ HRV > 0) between the forest and the urban groups for the first period (walks 1–4), the second period (walks 5–8), and for the whole intervention period (walks 1–8). Abbreviations: DP – difference in proportions. Bold font indicates statistical significance ($p < 0.05$).

Period	Group	Proportion of cases with Δ HRV > 0 vs. N	N	DP [95% CI]	χ^2 (df)	p	ϕ
1	Forest	0.66	105	0.14 [0.07, 0.27]	4.16 (1)	0.041	0.14
	Urban	0.52	106				
2	Forest	0.56	103	-0.03	0.21 (1)	> 0.6	–
	Urban	0.59	106				
1 & 2	Forest	0.61	208	0.06	1.26 (1)	> 0.2	–
	Urban	0.56	212				

5.3 Biomarkers

The mean difference between urban and forest environments on biomarkers (SCC, SAA, and HCC) is presented in Table 7. Salivary cortisol concentration means dropped by 1.38 ng/ml from baseline to endline in forest environment. On the other hand, participants who walked in urban environment had 0.32 ng/ml dropped in SCC. Salivary alpha-amylase result is contradictorily increased from morning to post-walking in both environments. Nonetheless, it decreased tremendously from 76.93 U/ml to 35.69 U/ml post-intervention mainly in urban environment, while it increased slightly from 46.96 U/ml to 47.94 U/ml in the forest environment. Furthermore, walking in forest induces a large drop in hair cortisol concentration by 12.81 pg/ml, meanwhile the opposite for urban walkers, who experienced an increase in hair cortisol concentration of as much as 15.54 pg/ml after the intervention. The corresponding results are further reflected from the log transformation of HCC, SCC, and SAA in Figure 12, Figure 13, and Figure 14, respectively.

Table 7. Mean difference biomarkers before and after intervention in urban vs. forest.

Urban							
Outcome	Baseline		MD Baseline	Endline		MD Endline	MD Endline – MD Baseline
	Morning	After walking		Morning	After walking		
	Mean [95% CI]			Mean [95% CI]			
SCC (ng/ml)	4.50 [3.67, 5.34]	0.89 [0.75, 1.02]	-3.61	4.89 [3.86, 5.92]	0.96 [0.79, 1.13]	-3.93	-0.32
SAA (U/ml)	64.06 [46.05, 82.06]	140.99 [95.33, 186.65]	76.93	66.08 [44.92, 87.24]	101.77 [75.57, 127.98]	35.69	-41.24
HCC (pg/ml)	13.85 (9.51, 18.18)		-	29.39 (4.08, 54.70)		-	15.54

Forest							
Outcome	Baseline		MD Baseline	Endline		MD Endline	MD Endline – MD Baseline
	Morning	After walking		Morning	After walking		
	Mean [95% CI]			Mean [95% CI]			
SCC (ng/ml)	4.90 [3.89, 5.91]	1.20 [0.83, 1.56]	-3.7	3.37 [2.65, 4.09]	1.05 [0.72, 1.38]	-2.32	-1.38
SAA (U/ml)	77.41 [45.94, 108.88]	124.37 [86.61, 162.13]	46.96	84.74 [40.01, 129.484]	132.68 [85.45, 179.92]	47.94	0.98
HCC (pg/ml)	32.36 [14.94, 49.78]		-	19.55 [10.61, 28.50]		-	-12.81

MD: Mean Difference

The results of linear mixed effect models are summarized in Table 8 (SCC), Table 9 (SAA), and Table 10 (HCC). Upon detailed examination of salivary cortisol concentration, we discovered a statistically significant difference. Specifically, cortisol levels were higher in the morning compared to after walking, with a significant interaction with the environment ($p < 0.05$). This indicates that salivary cortisol concentration in the forest environment is significantly lower than in an urban environment both before and after walking overtime (see Figure 12). Salivary alpha-amylase showed a significant difference based on sub-time (morning, after walking) with $p < 0.001$. This indicates that the morning salivary alpha-amylase level was lower than the after-walking salivary alpha-amylase level (refer to Figure 13). However, no interaction effect was observed in this model. The environment and time were not significantly associated with hair cortisol concentration. However, their interaction was significant (with $p < 0.01$), indicating that the decrease in hair cortisol levels from baseline to the endline was more pronounced in forest walkers compared to urban walkers. This result is visualized in Figure 14.

5.3.1 Salivary cortisol concentration

Table 8. Results of a linear mixed effect model for environment, time, and sub-time on salivary cortisol concentrations in older adults.

	Estimate	SE	df	t value	p
(Intercept)	0.271	0.022	48.461	12.542	< 0.001
Environment (Urban) ^a	0.003	0.022	48.461	0.124	0.902
Time (Baseline) ^b	0.025	0.013	151.022	1.868	0.064
Sub-time (Morning) ^c	0.315	0.013	148.575	23.980	< 0.001
Environment ^a x Time ^b	-0.032	0.013	151.022	-2.403	< 0.05
Environment ^a x Sub-time ^c	0.027	0.013	148.575	2.072	< 0.05
Time ^b x Sub-time ^c	0.012	0.013	148.575	0.951	0.343
Environment ^a x Time ^b x Sub-time ^c	-0.011	0.013	148.575	-0.854	0.395

Estimates refer to reference categories comparisons

^a Environment – Forest, ^b Time – Endline, ^c Sub-time – After walking

Significant effects are indicated in bold

Figure 12. Log transformed salivary cortisol concentration morning and after walking in urban (left) and forest (right) environments before and after intervention. Asterisk indicates a significant slope difference from baseline to endline particularly in morning SCC in forest environment. Interaction between environment and time is significant at $p < 0.05$. Interaction between environment and sub-time is significant at $p < 0.05$.

5.3.2 Salivary alpha-amylase

Table 9. Results of the linear mixed effect model for environment, time, and sub-time on salivary alpha-amylase in older adults

	Estimate	SE	df	t value	p
(Intercept)	1.840	0.041	51.650	44.416	< 0.001
Environment (Urban) ^a	-0.009	0.041	51.650	-0.211	0.834
Time (Baseline) ^b	0.011	0.015	152.900	0.707	0.481
Sub-time (Morning) ^c	-0.133	0.015	151.700	-8.984	< 0.001
Environment ^a x Time ^b	0.009	0.015	152.900	0.592	0.555
Environment ^a x Sub-time ^c	0.001	0.015	151.700	0.061	0.952
Time ^b x Sub-time ^c	-0.016	0.015	151.700	-1.079	0.282
Environment ^a x Time ^b x Sub-time ^c	-0.017	0.015	151.700	-1.117	0.266

Estimates refer to reference categories comparisons.

^a Environment – Forest, ^b Time – Endline, ^c Sub-time – After walking

Significant effects are indicated in bold

Figure 13. Log transformed salivary alpha-amylase in morning and after walking in urban (left) and forest (right) environments before and after intervention. In general, a significant difference appeared in sub-time (morning vs after walking) $p < 0.001$. A slight drop in SAA after walking in urban environment from baseline to endline.

5.3.3 Hair cortisol concentration

Table 10. Results of a linear mixed effect model for environment, and time on hair cortisol concentrations in older adults

	Estimate	SE	df	t value	p
(Intercept)	1.133	0.062	41.000	18.273	< 0.001
Environment (Urban) ^a	-0.048	0.062	41.000	-0.781	0.439
Time (Baseline) ^b	0.001	0.029	41.000	0.038	0.970
Environment ^a x Time ^b	-0.080	0.029	41.000	-2.805	< 0.01

Estimates refer to reference categories comparisons

^a Environment – Forest, ^b Time – Endline

Significant effects are indicated in bold

Figure 14. Log transformed hair cortisol concentration at baseline and at the end of the interventions in urban (gray) and forest (green) environments. Asterisk indicates a significant slope difference from baseline to endline for forest environment. Interaction between environment and time is significant at $p < 0.01$.

5.4 Cognitive functioning

Results of a two-way repeated measures ANOVA of the effects of time (within subjects, baseline to endline), environment (between subjects, forest vs. urban), and their interaction (time*environment) on the TMT-A, TMT-B, and TMT B-A scores are presented in Table 11 and Figure 15.

Table 11. Two-way repeated measures ANOVA of the effects of time (within subjects baseline to endline), environment (between subjects forest vs. urban), and their interaction (time*environment) on the TMT-A, TMT-B, and TMT B-A scores. Bold font indicates statistical significance ($p < 0.05$).

Outcome	Factor	<i>N</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	η^2p	95% CI η^2p
TMT A	Time	47	17.89	1	< 0.001	0.28	[0.08, 0.46]
	Environment	47	8.76	1	0.005	0.16	[0.02, 0.35]
	Interaction	47	0.01	1	> 0.9	–	–
TMT B	Time	47	20.25	1	< 0.001	0.31	[0.10, 0.48]
	Environment	47	5.32	1	0.026	0.11	[0.00, 0.28]
	Interaction	47	4.14	1	0.048	0.08	[0.00, 0.26]
TMT B-A	Time	47	5.7	1	0.021	0.11	[0.00, 0.29]
	Environment	47	0.59	1	> 0.4	–	–
	Interaction	47	4.3	1	0.044	0.09	[0.00, 0.26]

Figure 15. (A) Baseline to endline average scores for TMT-A; (B) Baseline to endline average scores for TMT-B; (C) Baseline to endline average scores for TMT B-A. The error bars indicate the 95% CI of the original means.

Pairwise comparisons indicated significant baseline to endline differences in TMT-A in both groups, in TMT-B only in the forest group, and in TMT B-A also in the forest group (Table 12). Differences between baseline and endline in TMT-A and TMT-B scores in both groups were produced partly by the repeated test administration after four weeks and partly by the intervention. Table 11 showed that the interaction between time and environment had no effect on TMT-A but significant effects on both TMT-B ($p = 0.048$) and TMT B-A ($p = 0.044$) scores. The interaction effect size η^2p on TMT-B ($\eta^2p = 0.08$) and TMT B-A ($\eta^2p = 0.09$) was medium.

Table 12. Pairwise comparisons between baseline and endline TMT scores (unit in second) in the urban and forest groups. Bold font indicates statistical significance ($p < 0.05$).

TMT measure	Group	<i>N</i>	Mean difference	95% CI η^2p	SE	<i>p</i>
TMT A	Urban	22	9.73	3.52, 15.94	3.08	0.003
	Forest	25	9.33	2.71, 15.95	3.29	0.007
TMT B	Urban	22	11.08	–	6.15	0.078
	Forest	25	29.36	16.16, 42.56	6.55	< 0.001
TMT B-A	Urban	22	1.35	–	5.84	> 0.8
	Forest	25	19.06	6.51, 31.60	6.23	0.004

Pre-intervention differences between the groups were detected in TMT-A at baseline and endline, as well as TMT-B at baseline (Table 13). There were no significant differences between TMT B-A scores in the two environments at baseline and endline. The intervention effect on the TMT scores was constituted through the interaction between time (within-subjects) and environment (between-subjects).

Table 13. Pairwise comparison between the urban and forest group TMT scores at baseline and endline (unit in second). CI was reported only for the significant. Bold font indicates statistical significance ($p < 0.05$).

TMT measure	Time	<i>N</i>	Mean difference	95% CI for mean difference	SE	<i>p</i>
TMT A	Baseline	47	10.72	1.65, 19.79	4.50	0.022
	Endline	47	11.12	2.80, 19.45	4.14	0.010
TMT B	Baseline	47	30.73	7.54, 53.93	11.52	0.011
	Endline	47	12.45	–	9.12	> 0.1
TMT B-A	Baseline	47	14.40	–	9.57	> 0.1
	Endline	47	-3.31	–	6.99	> 0.6

The effect of the interaction between time and environment on cognitive flexibility can also be expressed as TMT B-A baseline to endline decrease represented by the angular coefficient m , which was significantly steeper in the forest group than in the urban group (Table 14), indicating a positive medium-size effect of the forest intervention on the cognitive flexibility.

Table 14. Independent samples Student's t-test of the differences between the slopes of the decrease in TMT B-A according to environment. Bold font indicates statistical significance ($p < 0.05$).

Group	<i>N</i>	Mean	SD	Mean difference [95% CI]	df	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	Cohen's <i>d</i>
Forest	22	-0.64	1.15	0.6 [0.02, 1.16]	45	2.07	0.044	0.63
Urban	25	-0.04	0.79					

5.5 Quality of life

Although we did not find a significant difference between forest and urban environments for quality of life outcome (portrayed in Figure 16), the overall median scores of SF-36 indicate a good quality of life (Table 15). We found two components of mental health profoundly improved: emotional well-being ($Z = -3.169$, $p < 0.01$) in the forest group, and energy ($Z = -2.515$, $p < 0.05$) in urban group. General health, which is the sub-component of physical health, dropped by 5 scores in the forest environment ($Z = -2.035$, $p < 0.05$). We also noticed marginal significance for role functioning due to physical limitation ($Z = -1.651$, $p = 0.09$) and energy ($Z = -1.673$, $p = 0.09$) in forest group, whereas emotional well-being was close to a significant score ($Z = -1.953$, $p = 0.051$) in urban group.

Table 16 presents information about urban and forest SF-36 scores when participants experienced any improvement, constant, or deterioration along with the intervention given. In general, both environments equally experienced more improved quality of life than stagnant or deteriorated. We noticed only one component (general health) significantly differed between environment and quality of life status ($\chi^2 = 6.421$, $p < 0.05$).

Table 15. Median scores of SF-36 components between forest and urban environments before and after interventions.

Components	Forest				Urban			
	Baseline	Endline	Z	p	Baseline	Endline	Z	p
<i>Physical health</i>								
Physical functioning	80	80	-0.132	0.895	90	85	-0.024	0.981
Role functioning physical	62.5	68.75	-1.651	0.099	71.87	75	-1.23	0.216
Pain	67.5	67.5	-1.495	0.135	77.5	77.5	-0.770	0.441
General health	55	50	-2.035	0.042	55	55	-0.820	0.412
<i>Mental health</i>								
Emotional well-being	75	85	-3.169	0.002	77.5	80	-1.953	0.051
Role functioning emotional	75	66.66	-0.432	0.665	75	75	-0.696	0.487
Social functioning	75	87.5	-1.395	0.163	75	87.5	-1.147	0.251
Energy	68.75	62.5	-1.673	0.094	68.75	75	-2.515	0.012

Figure 16. Radar chart of median SF-36 sub-scores in forest and urban groups at baseline (black line) to endline (red line).

Table 16. Number of participants who experienced improved, unchanged, and deteriorated quality of life in urban and forest environment.

Quality of life	Forest			Urban			Pearson χ^2	<i>p</i>
	Improved	Constant	Deteriorated	Improved	Constant	Deteriorated		
<i>Physical health:</i>								
Physical functioning	8 (33.3%)	4 (16.7%)	12 (50%)	8 (30.8%)	8 (30.8%)	10 (38.5%)	2.275	0.321
Role functioning physical	14 (58.3%)	4 (16.7%)	6 (25%)	13 (50%)	7 (26.9%)	6 (23.1%)	0.776	0.678
Pain	13 (52%)	7 (28%)	5 (20%)	11 (42.3%)	8 (30.8%)	7 (26.9%)	0.547	0.761
General health	7 (28%)	3 (12%)	15 (60%)	11 (42.3%)	9 (34.6%)	6 (23.1%)	6.421	0.04
<i>Mental health:</i>								
Emotional well-being	20 (80%)	1 (4%)	4 (16%)	16 (61.5%)	4 (15.4%)	6 (23.1%)	2.809	0.245
Role functioning emotional	9 (37.5%)	4 (16.7%)	11 (45.8%)	11 (42.3%)	9 (34.6%)	6 (23.1%)	2.626	0.269
Social functioning	12 (48%)	6 (24%)	7 (28%)	10 (38.5%)	12 (46.2%)	4 (15.4%)	1.074	0.585
Energy/fatigue	15 (60%)	5 (20%)	5 (20%)	15 (57.7%)	7 (26.9%)	4 (15.4%)	0.425	0.809

6. DISCUSSION

The objective of the presented study was to determine the forest restoration effects on physiological and psychological responses, cognitive functioning, and quality of life in older adults. The obtained results allow for revisiting the working hypotheses: (a) Both forest and urban interventions are expected to lead to a reduction in stress levels and improvement in cognitive functions and quality of life, was not completely proved, particularly by the lack of association between improved cognitive flexibility and urban walks. However, quality of life components were proved (b) In contrast, forest walks were associated not only with sizeable improvement in cognitive flexibility but also with greater positive HRV changes than urban walks within the Johnson-Neyman region of significance ($p = 0.024$) and in the first intervention period ($p = 0.037$). Subsequently, SCC and HCC were reduced significantly after waking in forest environments. These findings lend support to the second hypothesis, particularly for stress reduction and improved cognitive function in the forest group. (c) The results partially align with the third hypothesis suggesting that the intervention effect size mainly on the cognitive function is greater than on HRV change. While it was true for the forest intervention, whose positive effect on the cognitive function and HRV change, relative to the urban intervention, was medium ($\eta^2_p = 0.09$) and small to medium (Cohen's $d = 0.28$), respectively, the urban intervention failed to produce a significant effect, especially on the executive functioning and cognitive flexibility. The results substantiated hypothesis (d), indicating that one or more environmental factors moderate the presumed intervention effects on older adults. Specifically, a decrease in ambient (air) temperature within the region of significance had contrasting effects on HRV outcomes, differing between forest canopies and open town squares. Moreover, hypothesis (e) proposing that unmanaged forests yield mental health benefits similar to those of forests managed for recreation was supported. This was evident from the HRV patterns observed after visits to the Mláčik natural forest, where no substantial deviation was noted compared to other forest locations. This consistency could be attributed to the presence of elements characterized by high fractal dimension, typical of old trees, which was recently shown to facilitate perceptual and cognitive flexibility. While not confirming all hypotheses in their entirety, the findings underscore the positive effects of forest environments in stress reduction and cognitive enhancement, as discussed in detail in the following subsections.

6.1 Heart rate variability

Pre- to post-walk HRV (RMSSD) increased significantly in both the forest and urban groups throughout the whole intervention. Significantly higher positive Δ HRV, also when represented in terms of the proportion of cases with Δ HRV > 0 relative to the total number of cases, was observed in the forest group compared to the urban group during the first two weeks of the intervention (walks 1–4) and when adjusted for the interaction between environment and ambient temperature. A narrowing of Δ HRV differences between the forest and urban environments was detected during the second sub-period, resulting from the interaction between environment and air temperature and its effect on Δ HRV, revealed by the Johnson-Neyman technique. As the average temperature dropped from 9.2 °C during the first period to 6.4 °C during the second intervention period, positive Δ HRV decreased under the forest canopy but increased in open urban settings without the effect of forest canopy shading. HRV (RMSSD) values can be expected to decline in non-thermally comfortable environments (Nkurikiyeyezu et al., 2017). Concurrently, it is possible that an adaptive change occurred after approximately four forest walks as a positive intervention outcome in the forest group members. The individual effect sizes of both interventions on HRV change were small to medium, but even minor individual-level effects can translate to large population health effects (Matthay et al., 2021). Some other studies detected no HRV differences between intervention outcomes from green areas or forest environments and those from built-up or industrial urban areas (Brown et al., 2014; Stigsdotter et al., 2017). However, they involved university students and office workers in shorter duration (approx. 20 min) exposures to distinct environments. A study by Song et al. (2015) found no significant difference between forest and city environments regarding the natural logarithm of LF/HF ($\ln(\text{LF}/\text{HF})$), an indicator of sympathetic nerve activity in middle-aged mainly when having hypertensive individuals. Additionally, a series from the previous study, which focused on healthy young women, explored various physiological responses, including blood pressure, and discovered that, when comparing the effects of walking in forest and urban settings, no statistically significant differences in participants' blood pressure changes, another physiological response. The average systolic blood pressure (SBP) values before walking were 95.6 ± 1.2 mmHg in the forest area and 95.9 ± 1.3 mmHg in the city area, with diastolic blood pressure (DBP) at 58.6 ± 1.0 mmHg in the forest and 58.8 ± 1.0 mmHg in the city. These values fell within the normal range, typically defined as 120–129/80–85 mmHg, with values below 120/80 mmHg often considered optimal. However, the study

noted that the mean blood pressure appeared relatively low, prompting consideration of interventions to bring the blood pressure to a more suitable level (Song et al., 2019)

Martinez et al. (2022), who, in agreement with the present study, also reported a significant but small relationship between perceived stress and HRV in IT workers, suggested that the association strength diminishes in real-life settings in the absence of specific and isolated stressors. This type of situation prevailed by design in our experiment before the documented bear sighting² as an uncontrolled event. We can only speculate that the incident could have had an impact on Δ HRV and the proportion of cases with positive HRV change via anxiety and the demand for sustained attention in the forest group members who eventually learned about it by word of mouth. The demand for sustained attention was shown to have an overriding effect on HRV decrement (Luque-Casado et al. 2016).

6.2 Biomarkers

While older individuals exhibit resilience traits stemming from life experience, wisdom, and the quality of relationships (Pichlerová et al., 2023), it is important to note that although depression is less common among older adults compared to younger adults, it can still have serious consequences. Stressful events have the potential to trigger depressive states, especially among the elderly, leading to severe outcomes (Fiske et al., 2009). As a result, minimizing and alleviating excessive stress in older adults is a crucial goal for desired environmental interventions.

Walking in green environments significantly alleviated salivary cortisol and hair cortisol concentration but the concentration was relatively stable for salivary alpha-amylase. Meanwhile, walking in a grey environment had little effect on salivary cortisol, a major impact on salivary alpha-amylase, but a negative effect on hair cortisol. These results indicated that when engaged in nature-based activity had a better impact on both acute and relative chronic stress. In contrast, engaging with grey-based activity had a positive effect on only acute stress.

Although we found limited synthesized evidence, particularly for hair cortisol and in

² While the study was implemented according to the protocol, one instance of brown bear sighting close to forests intervention site was reported by one participant and the driver in the second week of the intervention. Subsequently, two instances of anxiety and acute stress during forest walking were reported by another participant to the site assistant on duty. Similar events could potentially reduce the restorative effects of forests postulated by the stress recovery theory (Ulrich et al. 1991) and the attention restoration theory (Kaplan & Kaplan, 1989). In the Slovak context, between 2000 and 2015, there were 54 cases of brown bear attacks on humans (Bombieri et al., 2019). Possible anxiety and sustained attention induced by sighting a bear close to one of the forest localities could lead to the disappearance of Δ HRVB difference between the forest and urban groups.

older adults context, we found some previous studies that were consistent with our findings by taking into account, particularly stress biomarkers. First, Kobayashi et al. (2019) investigated the combined effects of walking (15 minutes), and the environment (urban vs forest) which found a decrease in salivary cortisol by 1.33 nmol/L when walking in forest environment, and 0.27 nmol/L dropped when walking in urban environment. Second, Park et al. (2010) compared walking (± 15 minutes) and viewing (± 15 minutes) experiences in forest and urban environments and discovered that the forest environment promotes lower salivary cortisol concentration than the urban environment. The effect was also significant for other measured outcome variables such as pulse rate, blood pressure, and HRV. Moreover, prior to this finding, he also investigated the impact of forest bathing by analyzing 12 male students with the experimental design involved two groups of 6 subjects each, with one group sent to a forest area and the other to a city area on the first day, and a cross-check on the second day. Subjects engaged in a 20-minute walk in the forenoon and subsequently observed the landscapes for 20 minutes in the afternoon. Physiological indices, including cerebral activity in the prefrontal area and salivary cortisol concentrations, were measured before and after these activities. The results revealed that cerebral activity in the prefrontal area of the forest group significantly decreased compared to the city group after walking. Additionally, the concentration of salivary cortisol in the forest group was significantly lower than that of the city group both before and after landscape observation. These findings suggest that forest bathing has a notable relaxing effect on both the physiological and psychological aspects of individuals, as evidenced by reduced cerebral activity and cortisol levels (Park et al., 2007). These studies, however, were conducted only for short-term exposure within two consecutive days of the experiment.

A contradictory finding was found by Gidlow et al. (2016) with a randomized cross-over study that exposed adults living in the West Midlands of the UK to the urban, natural, and water environments for 30 minutes within three consecutive days and found there were no differences in cortisol and heart rate variability as well as another outcome variable which was self-reported mood. This study observed reductions in cortisol across all environmental conditions, consistent with existing literature that generally fails to demonstrate environmental effects on cortisol. Instances of reported beneficial cortisol responses often have limitations, such as the absence of baseline data or potential confounders like variations in activity levels across environments. The magnitude of cortisol reductions observed in the study exceeded typical diurnal patterns, suggesting potential restorative effects, though this remains speculative without an inactive control condition. This study was in line with our

findings. However, we did find an interaction effect between environment and time, which is depicted in our linear mixed effect models, particularly for SCC and HCC.

Furthermore, a similar finding was found by Toda et al. (2013), who investigated the impact of walking in woodland on salivary stress markers, cortisol, and chromogranin A (CgA), in 20 healthy males. After the walk, CgA levels significantly increased, while cortisol levels remained unchanged. In control samples, both CgA and cortisol levels significantly decreased. Participants reported increased feelings of uplifted and tiredness, along with a significant reduction in subjective stress perception after the walk. These changes were not observed during the control period (resting in the office). This finding may be affected by walking activity, which could serve as a potential confounding factor. Indications such as elevated heart rate and increased fatigue suggest that the walk, particularly for elderly participants, might have been somewhat strenuous. Kirschbaum & Hellhammer (1994) postulated that exercises of moderate to high intensity can lead to heightened cortisol levels. Therefore, the physical stress induced by the demanding nature of the walk may have prevented the expected decrease, particularly in salivary cortisol levels in the woodland setting.

Although the studies have portrayed a positive effect of walking in a forested environment versus walking in an urban environment, the last two studies reported the opposite. The duration, frequency, walk intensity, and research setting might influence this interaction. Exposure to nature with various activities in short or long-term periods gives different health effects. Stier-Jarmer et al. (2021) collected evidence that the most effective intervention for nature-based activities and various mental and physical health outcomes was 8 to 12 weeks, and for optimal dosage ranged from 20 to 90 minutes. This study, however, did not include the cortisol biomarker in the search. A study from Zhang et al. (2023), nevertheless, collected cortisol biomarkers evidence from 17 studies and found that all salivary cortisol and serum cortisol levels were reduced significantly following the forest therapy regardless of the study period lengths. However, the effective duration appeared to be between two and six days.

In terms of salivary alpha-amylase, we found inconsistent results with previous studies, such as by Hunter et al. (2019), who discovered a profound drop of amylase by 28.1%/h after adjusting its diurnal rise of 3.5%/h but only for the least active participants during a month (at least three times per week) of flexible time intervention with students and staff of the University of Michigan (mean of age 45.8 yo) in the United States. In line with this study, Yamaguchi et al. (2006) also did a comparison effect after exercise in forest or

urban environment with university students (mean age: 22.2 yo) on the amylase activity and discovered that those who participated in forest exercise had 18% lower amylase in comparison those in an urban environment. Though our study found a diminutive incline in alpha-amylase for forest group (0.98 U/ml), physical activity may alter the main effect in which it influences the increase of salivary proteins that might be attributed to adrenergic activity, indicating a potential influence of stress response on the salivary composition (Dawes, 1981). The rise of plasma catecholamines (e.g., norepinephrine and epinephrine caused alpha-amylase to heighten during the exercise period (Thaysen et al., 1954). In addition, uncontrolled factors might alter the main effect on SAA, particularly in forest environments, as previously mentioned (nature-averse due to progressive animals or colder temperatures). Our result on SAA follows the HRV increase in the second fortnight for urban group walkers.

The hair cortisol as a chronic stress indicator impact from nature-based intervention is still scarce in this field. A study from Gidlow et al. (2016) that assessed the amount of natural environment within 132 healthy employed adults who addressed chronic stress revealed that those who lived in less dense green areas had higher chronic stress ($\beta = -.212$, $p=.019$). Although this study measured the effect of greenspaces on chronic stress objectively, it confirms the present experimental study that HCC markedly dropped while engaged in forested areas. Conversely, we found two studies were inconsistent with our findings. First, Choe & Sheffield (2022) investigated the potential synergy between a mindfulness-based stress reduction (MBSR) intervention and exposure to different environments (natural outdoor (park), built outdoor, and indoor settings) in managing stress-related symptoms. Ninety-nine participants underwent a six-week MBSR program, with depression, anxiety, and stress levels, and physiology assessed using the Depression Anxiety Stress Scales (DASS-21) at four-time points. Additionally, physiological changes in stress were measured through hair cortisol concentration (HCC) in participants who completed at least five MBSR sessions. While all groups showed changes in depression, anxiety, and stress levels during the intervention, the natural outdoor environment demonstrated more significant reductions in depression and stress compared to other settings. However, biological markers showed no significant differences in HCC were observed among the environments. The lack of sample size and the absence of a control group were the potential factors contributing to the no significant difference observed. The second study from Baena-Extremera et al. (2021) investigated the differences between athletes exercising outdoors (OG) and those exercising indoors (IG) in terms of stress, awareness, and fMRI activations

during the visualization of natural and urban images. Forty-nine participants underwent fMRI scans, completed stress and awareness scales, and provided hair cortisol samples. Viewing nature images, OG exhibited higher activation in the middle occipital cortex and a cluster including the supplementary motor area (SMA), premotor cortex, and pre-SMA compared to IG. In OG, greater left SMA activation negatively correlated with perceived stress, while in IG, increased premotor cortex activation positively related to Mindful Attention Awareness Scale scores. However, no significant association was found with hair cortisol levels (outdoor group 61.68 pg/mg and indoor group 62.37 pg/mg). This study suggests that outdoor exercise is associated with better psycho-emotional outcomes for athletes, and exposure to green nature activates brain areas linked to motor planning, emotion regulation, and emotional response. Limitations were found that cause and effect relationships might hinder the association of brain and emotion due to no clarity on whether brain functioning predicts or as a result of processing or regulating emotions. Secondly, the study encounters challenges in controlling participants' prior exposure to their sporting environment. Lastly, the study lacks qualitative data to support individuals' perceptions expressed in the psychological questionnaires, underscoring the importance of including such data in future research.

From all studies focused on stress biomarkers to the best of our knowledge, none of the experimental research studies that focused on the effect of forest bathing for a relatively long-term period (our case, 4 weeks), individually, in an older adult setting, which makes our study distinctive.

6.3 Cognitive function

Our study revealed a significant improvement in executive function and cognitive flexibility among participants who engaged in frequent individual forest walks, in comparison to those who walked in urban environments. The medium-size effect on cognitive flexibility manifested in the significantly steeper slope of the baseline to endline in TMT B-A decreased in the forest group compared to the urban group. These findings suggest that the forest intervention considerably enhanced the ability to switch between different mental sets, tasks, or strategies that constitute cognitive flexibility, as defined by Diamond (2013) and Miyake & Friedman (2012). Recent systematic reviews documented partial evidence for improved cognitive flexibility after exposure to natural environments (Ohly et al., 2016; Stevenson et al., 2018) coming almost entirely from studies with university students and the general population. The study by Setti et al. (2017) and Cassarino et al.

(2019) found an absence of cognitive restoration in older adults exposed to either natural or urban scenes on pictures.

Our study, exclusively centered on older adults has demonstrated that the notably enhanced cognitive flexibility observed was connected to walking in the forest amidst elements with high fractal dimensions. These elements, such as old trees (Seidel et al., 2019), were prevalent in all three forest intervention sites. Specifically, higher fractal complexity of nature scenes supports higher perceptual fluency (Franěk et al., 2019), and in turn, higher perceptual speed contributes to better cognitive flexibility (Cepeda et al., 2001). Relatedly, Davis et al. (2023) established that navigational and switching abilities demonstrated by highly mobile Bolivian 1st nation forager-farmers remained without significant decline at mid-life through older age (40–70 years old), owing to their exposure to complex forest environments.

6.4 Quality of life

Quality of life in general did not differ between environments (overall quality of life was nominally but not statistically improved in both environments). This is in line with previous studies; for instance, Kobayashi et al. (2021) reported the same pattern with respect to walking and viewing activities in both forest and urban environments, which showed a positive effect on the mood of 57 young Japanese university scholars. Besides, the largest public health intervention for physical activity “Walking for Health” study in the UK led by Marselle et al. (2013), found no significant differences in depression and positive effects, which are considered a crucial component of quality of life between the effect of environment type (natural places, green corridors, farmland, urban green space, coastal, urban public space, and mixture) in 708 subsampled participants.

However, majority of the previous studies reported the effects natural environment or exposure to nature had greater benefits on the various aspects of quality of life than the city areas. A study by Bacevičienė & Jankauskienė (2022) found nature exposure was attributed to a greater quality of life and also mediated the association of nature proximity (closeness to greenspaces) and quality of life. A long-term study focused on 664 employees found that people with natural exposure at work increased physical activity and hence increased the odds of belonging to long-term beneficial well-being after adjusting control variables (Korpela et al., 2017). Besides that, White et al. (2017) investigation focused on urban and peri-urban residents, revealing that individuals who engaged in more frequent

visits to natural environments reported higher levels of eudaimonic well-being even after controlling SES factors and other aspects of subjective well-being.

Despite the fact that we did not find a profound difference between the two investigated environments, when inspecting more detailed within-group differences, we found that emotional well-being was significantly improved after the intervention in forest walkers, while energy or vitality was significantly improved from baseline to endline in urban group. This is an interesting finding that aligns with the biophilia hypothesis suggesting that humans have an innate affinity for nature, and that the exposure to nature's aesthetic elements including fractal patterns and colors—such as the variegated colors of the trees assimilatory organs in October, i.e., the month, during which our study was performed contributes to emotional well-being (Wilson, 1984). Relatedly, Pichlerová et al. (2023) established that forest visitors perceived increased feelings of freedom and gratitude as positive emotions and in turn, Fagley (2012) suggested that appreciation and gratitude play a causal role in fostering well-being, possibly by reducing hedonic adaptation.

Furthermore, when comparing whether quality of life components were improved, stagnant, or deteriorated, we discovered both environments equally experienced more improved quality of life than stagnant or deteriorated. However, general health as part of the physical health component has deteriorated in forest walkers compared to urban walkers ($p = 0.04$). With this exception, restorative effects of the two outdoor activities were perceived by older adults as similar. We speculate that the urban walking effect was inflated by the mere presence and observation of other people on both town squares (even in the total absence of verbal exchange, in line with the study protocol), compared to practical solitude of subjects during forest walks. In other words, several dimensions of older adults' subjective well-being could have benefited from relational restoration that emphasizes supportive exchanges between people (Hartig, 2021). Additionally, walking conditions in forests, like uneven terrain and colder temperatures, might temporarily impact how people assessed their general health. Another explanation is that because older adults in the forest group were confronted with more challenging conditions, their post-intervention self-assessment reflected both the momentary recognition and an increased awareness of one's own physical health issues.

6.5 Patterns of forest intervention sites as the CES source

Established benefits for the mental health of older adults were derived from eight visits to three forest intervention sites in the course of one month. In line with the attention

restoration theory (Kaplan & Kaplan, 1989), specific benefits to the autonomic nervous systems were most likely involuntarily sourced from the presence of diverse forest tree species and variable forest structures. Specifically, ART posits that exposure to nature facilitates involuntary attention, providing relief from the demands of sustained focus and promoting mental restoration (Kaplan & Kaplan, 1989). Such involuntary attention was probably reinforced by the mixture of tree forest types – a spa forest managed specifically for restorative purposes, an urban forest managed for both recreation and timber production, and finally, the unmanaged mixed beech-fir-spruce forest in a nature preserve. Such a combination helped to reduce boredom and fatigue potentially instilled in forest visitors by frequent exposure to monotonous forest environments lacking variegated composition, structure, and color. The latter aspect was particularly relevant and appealing during the month of October, owing to the aesthetical values of variably colored assimilatory organs.

In parallel to ART, stress reduction theory (SRT) (Ulrich, 1983; Ulrich et al., 1991) emphasizes that the natural environment triggers a shift in feelings towards a more positive emotional state linked with attention and subsequent conscious processing. The conscious processing could occur immediately during forest walks since the experimental design did not allow for verbal communication during intervention, or later. Instead, forest intervention group members were encouraged to view the forest interior. The resulting impressions would be probably greatly diminished in the case of group visits format, in which the restoration might be primarily sourced from relational restoration. Significantly, old trees that were predominantly present in the unmanaged natural forest (Mláčik) improved the visual perception by rich fractal structures that facilitate perceptual fluency, cognitive flexibility, and emotional well-being (Wilson, 1984; Cepeda et al., 2001; Franěk et al., 2019). Thus, the presented study suggests that forest conservation and management should promote the availability of elements enhancing the complexity and fractal dimension of forest scenes, mainly the presence of old trees, to achieve a positive effect on health-related forest ecosystem services for older adults of paramount importance.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The presented dissertation demonstrated that participating in walking and viewing nature in forest environments with diverse structural features can notably enhance cognitive function, particularly cognitive flexibility. This effect is highly desired to counter cognitive decline in older adults, and it was not observed following the urban walking intervention. It is therefore plausible to attribute these specific benefits to causal chain starting from complex and optimally fractal structures, typical of mixed forests containing old trees, triggering the increase in perceptual fluency, and resulting in improved cognitive flexibility. Additionally, to a lesser extent, forest walking led to higher heart rate variability, which serves as a marker for parasympathetic activity in older adults and effectively lowered both acute and relative chronic stress levels. These results were mirrored by the results of biomarker analyses, mainly concerning saliva and hair cortisol levels. Although older people possess traits of resilience related to life experience, wisdom, and quality of relationships, stressful events may trigger depression with serious consequences in this demographic. It is therefore of paramount importance to mitigate excessive or chronic stress and its negative influences. Our findings concerning the decreases in post-intervention cortisol levels are novel with respects to the comparatively long intervention duration and provide support for forest walking as an efficient and easily available tool to mitigate stress, e.g., via increased emotional well-being. Although the difference in post-intervention effects of the two environments on the latter outcome was not statistically significant, it emerged as a strikingly conspicuous tendency.

Importantly, it should be emphasized that this study does not propose restricting these activities solely to wooded areas. To a lesser extent, urban walking has also demonstrated stress reduction, indicated by lower alpha-amylase levels and HRV in the experiment's second fortnight, and has shown improvements in various aspects of quality of life. However, if visiting and walking in either forest or urban settings is a matter of choice, our results clearly support the former alternative. Crucially, urban walking may be more suitable, convenient, or safe for highly fragile elderly individuals, sensitive to factors negatively affecting their general physical health. Such an opinion is substantiated by our analyses of the Quality of Life questionnaires.

The implications of our findings extend to public health and forest ecosystem management, underscoring the need for policies that facilitate access to forests and green

spaces. Such policies can support cognitive function and mental health, ultimately improving the overall quality of life for older adults. To actualize these benefits, collaboration between experts in public health and forest management and other related actors is crucial to develop and implement scalable frameworks. These frameworks should address the selection, design, and maintenance of suitable forest restorative areas, with a specific focus on meeting the needs of older adults, including safety and accessibility. Further research should focus on analyzing patterns of HRV change throughout interventions to capture the potential influence of other modulators and conditioning factors, such as biophobia. The latter factor gains attention in the public debate revolving around efforts to rewild nature in many parts of Europe, in which many large mammal and apex predator species were exterminated in the past, and should be paid attention to for twofold reasons: to ensure safe restorative forest environments for the vulnerable elderly demographic on the one hand, and to limit the often unnecessary and debilitating fear and the resulting emotions on the other hand. Using adequate and targeted restorative areas supervision, combined with clear and easily accessible, and interpretable data and instructions, could provide a remedy in the current situation. Also, the optimum intervention length and frequency of intervention warrants further investigation. A targeted forest-based intervention could lead to a reduction in the minimum required exposure duration compared to those currently recommended.

Finally, implementing nature-based therapy not only directly impacts health and well-being but also enhances the vitality and productivity of the elderly, potentially contributing to their post-retirement life when retirement age policies are extended and require their expertise. Importantly, ensuring the availability of green spaces can make a significant contribution to planetary health.

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LIST OF ANNEXES

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Annex I. Differences between forest and urban environment for all Garmin features and mean score of cognitive function

Table S1. Independent t-test for Garmin features between forest and urban environment

Garmin features	Forest	Urban	df	t-value	p
	Mean				
Steps	7285.370	7054.331	41.694	0.252	0.802
Deep sleep	1.427	1.247	46.338	0.857	46.338
Light sleep	4.548	4.613	48.539	-0.387	0.700
Rapid eye movement	1.507	1.614	47.286	-0.810	0.422
Sleep duration	7.196	7.322	39.484	-0.513	0.611
Respiration sleep	16.286	14.852	41.633	3.179	0.003
Respiration awake	14.222	14.030	48.680	0.942	0.351
Heart rate	71.040	69.427	39.093	0.859	0.396
Stress level	31.926	30.888	48.197	0.730	0.469

Table S2. Mean score of cognitive function by environments.

Cognitive functions	Forest		Urban	
	Baseline	Endline	Baseline	Endline
TMT A	69.34 (21.39)	59.08 (20.08)	54.52 (12.34)	45.27 (10.73)
TMT B	157.90 (58.30)	126.47 (51.74)	123.12 (46.44)	107.23 (40.09)
TMT B-A	79.78 (38.53)	57.88 (20.98)	66.54 (43.66)	59.72 (30.75)

Annex II. Ethical approval conducting intervention study (provided merely the first page due to confidentiality)

ETICKÁ KOMISIA
Úrad Banskobystrického samosprávneho kraja
Nám. SNP 23, 974 01 Banská Bystrica, Slovak Republic

ETHICS COMMITTEE

ROZHODNUTIE LOKÁLNEJ ETICKEJ KOMISIE
LOCAL ETHICS COMMITTEE DECISION

Protokol: <i>Protocol:</i>	N/A
EudraCT č.: <i>EudraCT No.:</i>	N/A
Názov štúdie:	Výskum vplyvu pobytu v lesnom prostredí na subjektívnu pohodu, stres a kognitívnu funkciu staršej populácie (60+)
Koordinátor projektu :	Medicínske centrum Univerzity v Leidene, Holandsko (The Leiden University Medical Centre–LUMC)
Partneri projektu:	University of Newcastle Upon Tyne (Veľká Británia) University Of Northumbria At Newcastle (Veľká Británia) Percuros BV (Holandsko) TecoBioSciences GmbH (Nemecko) Innosco BV (Holandsko)

Odber vzorky slín pre určenie kortizolu s použitím salivetiek

Súprava na odber vzorky slín obsahuje štyri skúmavky:

- skúmavky **A** a **B** použijete v prvý deň intervencie, t.j. v deň, keď pôjdete na prvú prechádzku
- skúmavky **C** a **D** sa použijú v posledný deň intervencie, t.j. v deň Vašej poslednej prechádzky v rámci výskumu
- vzorka slín do skúmavky **A** sa odoberie **15 minút po prebudení**
- vzorka slín do skúmavky **B** sa odoberie **20 minút po intervencii**, t.j. prechádzke
- pri použití skúmaviek **C** a **D** sa postupuje rovnako ako pri skúmavkách **A** a **B**

POSTUP na odber vzorky slín:

Krok 1

Pred spaním si pripravte **skúmavku A**, pero, papier a hodinky na nočný stolík.

Krok 2

15 minút po rannom prebudení:

- zostaňte ležať v posteli/relaxujte (bez česania, použitia zubnej nite, rúžu, balzamu na pery)
- vezmite **skúmavku A**, otvorte horný kryt (neodstraňujte držiak, na ktorom je umiestnený vatový tampón)

Krok 3

Vložte vatový tampón do úst (nepoužívajte pri tom prsty).

Krok 4

Vatový tampón žujte a omieľajte v ústach najmenej **2 minúty** (skontrolujte si čas). Uistite sa, že vatový tampón je úplne mokrý.

Krok 5

Vyplňte vatový tampón späť do skúmavky (nepoužívajte pri tom prsty, perami sa nedotýkajte skúmavky). Na vloženie špongie do skúmavky je možné použiť zuby.

Krok 6

Zatvorte skúmavku horným uzáverom a skúmavku so vzorkou slín vložte do chladničky.

Krok 7

Skúmavku **A** aj **B** so vzorkou slín vyzdvihne náš asistent u Vás doma.

Annex IV. Research assistant meeting instruction

POZNÁMKY ASISTENTOM VÝSKUMU – stretnutia s testovaním miesto: Kongresové centrum TUZVO – internát Ľ. Štúra

- na stretnutie prosíme prísť cca 15 min pred oficiálnym začiatkom, ak to je možné
- pri začatí testovania – usadíte seniora k jednému z pripravených stolov (stoly sú oddelené paravanmi), pri ktorom budú vyplňať testy a dotazníky:
 - *Test cesty – časť A*
 - *Test cesty – časť B*
 - dotazník *Vaše zdravie a pohoda*
 - dotazník *Základné dáta*
 - dotazník *X-2*
- seniora poprosíte o to (prosíme vždy aj skontrolujte), aby si **čitateľne** vypísal meno, kde sa to vyžaduje (na *Test cesty – časť A*, *Test cesty – časť B*, dotazník *Vaše zdravie a pohoda*, dotazník *Základné dáta*). *Test X-2* bude označený numericky, číslom, ktoré prislúcha danému seniorovi (prosím o kontrolu v zozname, ktorý dostanete)
- pri *Test cesty – časť A*, *Test cesty – časť B* postupujte podľa návodu, ktorý ste obdržali, najprv s ním prejdite „zácvik“ a potom samotný test (postupujte podľa návodu), majte pripravené stopky, čas zapíšte čitateľne priamo na test
- na otázky v dotazníkoch *Vaše zdravie a pohoda*, *Základné dáta* a *X-2* senior odpovedá sám

ZOZNAM SENIOROV počas testovacích dní Vám bude k dispozícii v príslušný deň testovania. Testovania sú v nasledovné termíny s nasledovnými počtami seniorov:

deň	čas	počet
ŠTVRTOK – 30.10.2021	o 15:00	5
PIATOK – 1.10.2021	o 9:00	7
	o 10:00	8
	o 11:00	9
	o 12:00	8
	o 14:00	6
	o 16:00	3
SOBOTA – 2.10.2021	o 11:00	5